

“Neuronal Correlates of Occulometric Parameters in Face Recognition”

Master Thesis

Revision 5061220900¹ of this document was
presented to the Faculty of Biosciences
at the Ruprecht-Karls-Universität Heidelberg

Horea-Ioan Ioanăș

2014

¹<https://github.com/TheChymera/masterarbeit/tree/50612209002bb6e0423f7ec57db404fef4ace593>

This thesis was written at the **Central Institute of Mental Health** at the University of Heidelberg in the period of **2013-06-06** to **2013-12-10** under supervision of **Prof. Dr. Peter Kirsch**. This version was updated **2014-01-31** to reflect a more current interpretation of the project.

1st Appraiser: Prof. Dr. Rainer Spanagel Institute: Central Institute of Mental Health

2nd Appraiser: Prof. Dr. Daniel Durstewitz Institute: Central Institute of Mental Health

I herewith declare that I wrote this Master thesis independently under supervision and used no other sources and aids than those indicated.

.....
Date

.....
Signature

.....

The thesis has to contain a summary in English.

In addition to the faculty advisers mentioned in the preamble of this document, we would like to explicitly give thanks to a number of other members of the department of clinical psychology at the Central Institute of Mental Health in Mannheim. Their expertise in designing and performing experiments, and analysing results was instrumental to the success of this thesis.

- Martin Gerchen
- Carina Sauer
- Daniela Mier
- Gabriela Stoessel

We would also like to extend our gratitude to the numerous other people with whom we have interacted in the process of writing this thesis, and whose goodwill and effort made a significant difference pertaining to the quality of this work.

- Øystein Bjørndal, of the Norwegian Defence Research Establishment
- Ben Bolker, of McMaster University
- Denis A. Engemann, of the Juelich Research Centre in Cologne
- Laurent Gautier, of the Technical University of Denmark
- Marek Hlavac, of Harvard University
- Philip Leifeld, of the University of Konstanz
- Christopher Loudon, of the University of Texas
- Geoffrey M. Poore, of Union University

Contents

1	Summary	7
1.1	English	7
1.2	German	8
2	Background	9
2.1	Pupillometry	10
2.2	Pupil Dilation Response	11
2.3	Pupil Dilation and the Locus Coeruleus	13
2.4	Locus Coeruleus	14
2.5	Focus	16
3	Methods	17
3.1	Participants	17
3.1.1	Trial Procedure	17
3.2	Visual Matching Task	17
3.2.1	Trial Sequences	18
3.2.2	Visual Composition	19
3.3	Stimulus Images	21
3.3.1	Emotional Faces	21
3.3.2	Scrambled Images	21
3.4	Occulometry	23
3.4.1	Eye Tracking	23
3.4.2	Pupillometry	23
3.5	Functional MRI	24
3.5.1	Data Acquisition	24
3.5.2	Data Processing	24
3.6	Statistical Analysis	26
3.6.1	Paired T-Test	27

3.6.2	Standard Error of the Mean	27
3.6.3	ANOVA	28
3.6.4	Mixed Models	28
3.6.5	Pearson's r	29
3.7	Questionnaires	29
3.8	Genetic Material Samples	30
4	Excursus: Preliminary Experiments	33
4.1	Background	33
4.2	Focus	33
4.3	Methods	34
4.3.1	Participants	34
4.3.2	Visual Matching Task	34
4.3.3	Stimulus Images	36
4.3.4	Data Post-Processing	38
4.4	Results	38
4.4.1	Cluster-Based Scrambling	38
4.4.2	Composite (Kernel-and-Cluster-Based) Scrambling	42
4.5	Discussion	45
4.5.1	Final Model Quality Assessment	45
4.5.2	Reaction Times	47
4.5.3	Error Rates	48
4.5.4	Data Reliability	48
5	Results	49
5.1	Participant Response Analysis	49
5.1.1	Reaction Times	49
5.1.2	Error Rates	51
5.2	Pupillometry - Methodological Reliability	52
5.3	Per-Condition Pupil Dilation Response	53
5.3.1	Time-Agnostic Comparison	53
5.3.2	Task Engagement: Trial vs. Inter-Trial	55
5.3.3	Difficulty: Easy vs. Difficult Trials	55
5.3.4	Emotionality: Emotional vs. Scrambled Trials	57
5.3.5	Emotion: Happy vs. Fearful Emotion Trials	58
5.4	Condition-Dependent Brain Activity Contrasts	60

5.4.1	Difficult vs. Easy Pattern Matching	60
5.4.2	Emotion vs. Pattern Recognition	60
5.4.3	Strong vs. Weak emotion Intensity	64
5.5	Pupil Dilation Regression	65
6	Discussion	69
6.1	Pyxrand's Stimuli for Non-Semantic Matching	69
6.2	Pupillometric Time Course	70
6.2.1	Method Viability	70
6.2.2	Task Difficulty	71
6.2.3	Task Type Effect	72
6.2.4	Emotional Valence Effect	72
6.2.5	Per-Condition Brain Activation	73
6.2.6	Pupil Area Correlated LC Activity	74
6.2.7	Outlook	75
7	Supplementary Material	85
7.1	Non-Definitive Preliminary Experiment Runs	87

Chapter 1

Summary

1.1 English

Pupillometry is a simple physiological method with ample applications in neuropsychology. Electrophysiological studies indicate pupil dilation control via the locus coeruleus, the main site of norepinephrine synthesis in the brain. We use functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to test whether the pupil dilation response is a reliable indicator of locus coeruleus activity, and whether any incongruences between these measures can be accounted for by the type of activity being performed during brain imaging. Additionally, we use a behavioural task based on both emotion and pattern recognition and test whether: (a) emotional perception impacts the pupil dilation response differently from equivalent non-emotional cognitive load; (b) perception of different emotions influences the pupil dilation response differently. We are complementing our neuroimaging and behavioural experiments with psychometric and genetic assays - the results of which may help pursue further ramifications of our work in psychology as well as in biology. Our study uncovers a significant correlation of pupil dilation and locus coeruleus activity, which we believe can pave the way for establishing pupillometry as a convenient, rapid, and low-cost avenue of approximating noradrenergic activity. Additionally, we present novel data on pupil dilation time courses in face matching trials, which are contingent upon task difficulty and emotional valence of stimuli. We enrich the informative potential of the above and the transparency of our work by implementing the very latest open science concepts and technologies.

1.2 German

Die Pupillometrie ist eine einfache physiologische Untersuchungsmethode, die weitläufige Anwendungen in der Neuropsychologie findet. Elektrophysiologische Befunde deuten auf eine Kontrolle der Pupillendilatation über dem Locus Coeruleus, dem Hauptsyntheseort für Norepinephrin im Gehirn, hin. Wir benutzen funktionelle Magnetresonanztomographie (fMRI) um zu überprüfen, ob Pupillenweitung zuverlässig Aufschluss über neuronale Aktivität im Locus Coeruleus gibt, und ob eventuelle Unstimmigkeiten dieser Messungen auf die Art der ausgeführten Testaufgabe während des bildgebenden Verfahrens zurückzuführen sind. Zusätzlich benutzen wir einen sowohl auf Emotions- wie auch auf Mustererkennung basierenden Verhaltenstest, um zu ermitteln ob: (a) sich Emotionserkennung anders auf die Pupillenweitung auswirkt als äquivalente nicht-emotionale kognitive Auslastung; (b) die Wahrnehmung verschiedener Emotionen die Pupillenweitung unterschiedlich beeinflusst. Wir ergänzen die obigen Untersuchungen indem wir Tests für die psychometrische und genetische Typisierung der Probanden durchführen, deren Auswertung dabei helfen könnte die Relevanz unserer Untersuchung sowohl für die Psychologie als auch für die Biologie zu stärken. Wir entdecken eine signifikante Korrelation von Pupillenweitung und Locus Coeruleus Aktivität, und vermuten dass diese den Weg für die Etablierung der Pupillometrie als ein unumständliches und kostengünstiges Verfahren zur Approximierung neuroadrenerger Aktivität bahnen kann. Zusätzlich präsentieren wir neue Daten zum Zeitverlauf der Pupillenweitung in Verhaltenstests zur Gesichtserkennung. Diese Zeitverläufe werden laut unseren Ermittlungen sowohl durch die Schwierigkeit der Aufgabe, wie auch durch die emotionelle Valenz der Stimuli moduliert. Wir bereichern den informativen Wert und die Transparenz unserer Arbeit durch die Anwendung neuester Open Science Konzepte und Technologien.

Chapter 2

Background

Non-invasive measurement tools for neuronal activity in humans have become increasingly powerful in recent years. In spite of this, activity in deep brain structures (most commonly assayed via functional magnetic resonance tomography or positron emission tomography) remains difficult to measure without both immobile and very costly equipment.

Deep brain structures - especially midbrain monoaminergic nuclei (such as the ventral tegmental area, the raphe nuclei, or the locus coeruleus) - project axons into large portions of the cortex [van Domburg and ten Donkelaar, 1991; Hornung, 2003; Loughlin et al., 1982], thus being of relevance to many mental processes and disorders. As these nuclei contain neurons prevalently producing one neurotransmitter (dopamine, serotonin, and noradrenaline respectively), measuring their activity can add valuable information to brain activation maps (of which many are currently neurotransmitter-agnostic). This added information can also encourage the formulation and testing of hypotheses pertaining to specific cell-level signal transduction pathways for activity observed in the brain areas these nuclei innervate.

Developing portable, low-cost means of assessing the activity of any of the noted nuclei would be a significant breakthrough for neuropsychology. Such a method would bring advances especially in the study of phenomena wherefore brain imaging study attendance is inhibitive (such as social interaction, self-administered drug use, decision-making in natural settings, or spontaneous phenomena - epiphanies, déjà vus, etc.). To this end we explore pupillometry as a possible avenue towards developing such a method - with expected relevance mainly to locus coeruleus activity, but also with possible implications for the serotonergic system and the raphe nuclei.

2.1 Pupillometry

Pupillometry refers to the long-standing physiological method of measuring pupil diameter. Sporadic studies involving pupil diameter measurements have been performed as early as the beginning of the XIX. century [Loewenfeld and Lowenstein, 1958]- with the establishment of a scientific community around pupillometry following about one and a half centuries later. The early emergence of pupillometric research owes to the innovation of infra-red imaging to study the eye [Dubois-Poulsen et al., 1955] around the middle of the XX. century (originally for ophthalmologic purposes, where pupillometry also continues to be used [Thompson, 2012]). This development made it possible to measure pupil kinetics without interference from the measurement equipment itself - and remains a standard for even the newest devices of our day [Bradley et al., 2010].

Pupillometry has been in documented use in psychology since 1960, when Hess and Polt published what was arguably the seminal paper of psychophysiological pupillometry in the journal *Science* [Hess and Polt, 1960]. In this publication they reported presenting images of partly nude adults and babies to a small sample of participants, and observing increased pupil dilation in males to stimuli depicting women, and increased pupil dilation in women to stimuli depicting either males or babies. In light of this manifold interpretable finding, research over the following decade has focused on making the case that pupil dilation is a marker of attraction, or well-being.

Many early publications present varying concepts related to the initial publication by Hess and Polt, and report a robust modulation of pupil diameter by sexual attraction [Goldwater, 1972; Hess et al., 1965] or positive affect [Nunally et al., 1967; Bradshaw, 1967]. Even some of these early papers, however, hint at a broader phenomenon underlying neuropsychological control of pupil size. This broader phenomenon was initially termed “general activation” [Nunally et al., 1967], and has over the years been more accurately identified as “cognitive load” [Laeng et al., 2011; Zekveld et al., 2011], “attention” [Wykowska et al., 2013; Kraemer et al., 2000], or - most recently - “control state” [Hayes and Petrov, 2013]. Of late, researchers have tentatively tried to establish pupillometry as an indicator of neuronal activity in the Locus Coeruleus (LC; more on this in section 2.4) [Gilzenrat et al., 2010]. In the research herein presented, we have sought to test the viability of pupillometry as an assessment not of a neuropsychological phenomenon, but of a neurological phenomenon (LC activation) - complementing (the mostly behavioural) previous approaches [Gilzenrat et al., 2010; Granholm and Steinhauer, 2004] with concomitant brain imaging.

2.2 Pupil Dilation Response

Pupillary dilation (mydriasis) is most prominently known as a physiological reaction to low light conditions [Ellis, 1981]. However, a broad range of mental states - such as alertness [Yoss et al., 1970], arousal [Bradshaw, 1967], fatigue [Morad et al., 2000], and surprise [Preuschoff et al., 2011] - have also been shown to modulate pupil dilation. Additionally, application of numerous substances (topically and/or systemically) is known to affect pupil dilation [Theofilopoulos et al., 1988; Bye et al., 1979; Phillips et al., 2000]; to the extent that the method is used to assess drug effects in laboratory animals [Murray and Loughnane, 1981]. Disregulation in tonic pupil dilation is well known in the medical community as a presenting sign for various neurological conditions [Caglayan et al., 2013]. The phenomenon has, however, also been implicated in non-neuropathic diseases, most notably in autism spectrum disorders [Anderson et al., 2013].

The direct control mechanism of pupil dilation (or contraction for that matter) consists of two smooth muscle sets located in the iris: the iris dilator muscle and the iris sphincter muscle.

- The iris dilator is a radial muscle located anterior of the pigment epithelium of the iris, and chiefly responsible for iris dilation. This muscle is innervated by the sympathetic nervous system and is controlled via noradrenergic stimulation of its α_1 -adrenergic receptors [van Alphen, 1976].
- The iris sphincter muscle is located anterior of the iris dilator muscle and chiefly responsible for iris contraction. Its innervation stems from the parasympathetic system and is mainly mediated by M_3 -muscarinic acetylcholine receptors [Woldemussie et al., 1993; Taylor, 1974].

It should be noted that counterbalanced neurotransmitter effects (such as direct cholinergic inhibition of the iris dilator muscle) have also been documented [Yoshitomi et al., 1985].

In light of these characteristics it is not surprising that topical application of drugs can affect pupil dilation. This phenomenon is especially robust and well-documented for cholinergic agonists [Smith and Smith, 1978] and antagonists [Gambill et al., 1967] - to the extent that pupil dilation is used as an assay for in vivo anticholinergic effects [Bye et al., 1979]. Serotonin (5-HT) receptors have also been shown to exert an influence on pupil dilation - which has been demonstrated either by topically applied serotonin [Koella and Schaeppi, 1962], or by systemically applied 5-HT receptor agonists [Yu et al., 2004]. Systemic application of 5-HT receptor agonists (in rats) has furthermore been shown to elicit mydriasis not via peripheral

5-HT receptors, but via central nervous system (CNS) 5HT_{1A} receptors.

Considerable attention was received by the hypothesis that CNS 5-HT (in liaison with the long-standing interest of pupillometrists in affect - detailed under section 2.1) may be chiefly implicated in controlling pupil dilation. As a most prominent example of pupil-dilation and serotonin interaction, antidepressants of the selective serotonin re-uptake inhibitor (SSRI) class are documented to cause tonic mydriasis [Fitzgerald and Bronstein, 2013; Klein-Schwartz et al., 2012].

Relying on this established phenomenon, at least one study has tried to investigate the value of pupil dilation as a convenient, semi-quantitative 5-HT biomarker [Noehr-Jensen et al., 2009]. The study found an escitalopram-correlated reduction of light-evoked pupil constriction, but no overall effect of escitalopram (a drug of the SSRI class which the authors use as a proxy for systemic 5-HT) on pupil dilation. The authors conclude that pupillometry can, thus, not be used as a 5-HT biomarker. In this context we would, however, like to remark that theirs was a chronic test for tonic dilation. In fact, the modulation of the pupillary light reflex found by the authors may even indicate that the outcome of their study would have been quite different, had it employed pupillometry to assay phasic dilation related to acute events (such as for instance in a behavioural task). In any case, the results of this study conflict with the often reported dose-dependent pupil dilator activity of SSRIs [Nielsen et al., 2010; Fitzgerald and Bronstein, 2013; Klein-Schwartz et al., 2012]; and need not dismiss all hopes of pupillometry as a serotonin biomarker.

Evidence has mounted considerably faster and more consistently on establishing pupil diameter as a biomarker for noradrenaline (NA). In light of this, it may be hypothesized that 5-HT works upstream of NA in controlling pupil dilation; and this may lead to the opaquer state of research concerning the correlation of 5-HT and pupil dilation compared to the correlation of NA and pupil dilation. Research into the pupil dilation effects of 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA) administered in the presence of varying monoamine reuptake inhibitors and monoamine agonists has - however - shown that 5-HT and NA have both an independent and a synergistic effect on pupil dilation [Hysek and Liechti, 2012]. In this study the pupil dilation response changes prompted by MDMA were modulated by the NA reuptake inhibitor (SNRI) reboxetine and the 5-HT and NA reuptake inhibitor (SNRI) duloxetine, but not by the α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist clonidine.

A number of systemic interactions between the 5-HT and NA neurotransmitter systems may also be of relevance to the effects of 5-HT and NA on pupil dilation. One such interaction reveals itself in the fact that systemic 5-HT increase - as mediated by SSRI administration -

has been documented in both anxiety [Blier and El Mansari, 2007] and cardiovascular [Barton et al., 2007] studies to reduce sympathetic (noradrenergic) activation over time. Other, more direct, interactions could also arise from the fact that noradrenergic neurons projecting from the LC synapse onto the serotonergic neurons of the dorsal and caudal nucleus raphe in the brainstem [Samuels and Szabadi, 2008]. Though these findings indicate a high probability synergistic effects, we believe it reasonable and more transparent to first investigate NA mediated pupil dilation independently of 5-HT.

A noradrenergic sensitivity of pupil dilation has been demonstrated in studies with the α_2 -adrenergic receptor agonist clonidine, and the (more broad spectrum) α_2 -adrenergic receptor antagonist yohimbine [Phillips et al., 2000]. As would be expected from the aforementioned findings (and with the α_2 -adrenoceptor being mainly an autoreceptor), clonidine lead to a decrease in pupil diameter while yohimbine lead to an increase; co-administration showed that these effects counteract each other.

2.3 Pupil Dilation and the Locus Coeruleus

Strengthening the association between the NA system and pupil dilation, evidence from electrophysiology studies performed in macaques [Rajkowski et al., 1994] shows a strong correlation and time-lock between neuronal firing in the main noradrenergic nucleus of the brain (the locus coeruleus) and pupil dilation. Researchers have sought to further validate the connection between pupil dilation and LC neuronal activity by testing the correlation between pupil response and phenomena which are considered markers of LC activity.

One accessible avenue of doing so is pupil-dilation to LC matching via behavioural patterns [Gilzenrat et al., 2010]. In the referenced study authors observe that tonic pupil dilation correlates with exploratory behaviour and task disengagement, while phasic pupil dilation correlates with increased task engagement; they argue that this closely mimics documented [Aston-Jones and Cohen, 2005] changes in behaviour upon tonic or phasic LC activity. In the review of this study it is very important to note that pupil dilation correlates *not* with task difficulty per se, but with task engagement - meaning that if a task is too difficult to fulfil, pupil diameter may not see a phasic increase. Interestingly, similar pupil dilation kinetics have been found during off-line thought [Smallwood et al., 2011], and have been again put into liaison with noradrenergic LC activity (as this is known to play a pivotal role in attention control - more under section 2.4).

Other researchers have tried to test the correlation between physiological phenomena which

are strongly suspected of being LC-mediated, and make the case that good correlation between these strengthens the probability of a common cause (the only candidate for which would be LC activation) [Murphy et al., 2011]. In the annotated example the authors test pupil dilation kinetics against the P3 (also P300) event-related potential (known for its role in decision-making [Champan and Bragdon, 1964] and attention [Picton, 1992]) and observe a strong and positive correlation.

Tests using more direct assessments of LC activation in humans are scarce, traditionally due to methodological restrictions. The advent of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) has also had less impact here than in research on other brain areas due to the nonstandard blood-oxygen level dependent (BOLD) response patterns of brainstem structures and the small size of the nucleus [Astafiev et al., 2010].

2.4 Locus Coeruleus

The Locus Coeruleus (LC) is a bilateral brainstem nucleus located in the pons, close to the superior cerebellar pedunculi. Its name and original identification base on the (very faintly) blue appearance of the nucleus in fresh brain tissue [Maeda, 2000]. The distinctive blue colour is attributed to monoamine (in this case noradrenaline) polymerization and is analogous to the colouring of other brainstem nuclei such as the substantia nigra [Mai and Paxinos, 2011]. The right nucleus of the LC has been documented to comprise approx. 33.600 catecholaminergic cells, while the cell count of the left nucleus lies at about 39.100 [Mouton et al., 1994]. While post mortem dissection-based coordinates for the LC have been documented for centuries [Maeda, 2000], in vivo magnetic-resonance determined coordinates have only recently emerged [Keren et al., 2009]. We believe that in light of prospective fMRI study, these data serve as a far better guideline.

LC activity has been originally identified in response to various painful stimuli, has gradually been expanded to include first non-painful threat signals [Grant and Redmond, 1984], and subsequently many more events. The LC is known chiefly for its role in noradrenergic neuronal transmission [Benarroch, 2009], and based on this has been implicated in a wide range of phenomena, exceeding but including:

- Anxiety [Weiss et al., 1994]
- Attention [Benarroch, 2009]
- Autism [Mehler and Purpura, 2009]
- (Emotional) Arousal [Bangasser et al., 2011]
- Depression [Weiss et al., 1994]

- Drug Use [Samuels and Szabadi, 2008]
- Psychological Stress [Bangasser et al., 2011]
- Neural plasticity [Benarroch, 2009]
- Posture and Balance [Benarroch, 2009]
- Neurodegenerative Symptoms [Gesli et al., 2000]

From the point of view of pupillometry-based neuronal activity assay, the LC is of interest due to the documented correlation and time-lock between pupil dilation and LC neuron activity in macaques [Rajkowski et al., 1994]. Further electrophysiological findings in macaques coming from the same authors [Rajkowski, 2004] found a strong correlation and time-lock between reaction times in behavioural trials and phasic firing of single neurons in the LC. Homogeneous results all over the LC additionally prompted the authors to conclude that - at least in view of this paradigm - LC neurons are physiologically similar across the nucleus [Rajkowski, 2004].

The noradrenergic activity of the LC is chiefly implicated in attention control [Aston-Jones et al., 1994; Gabay et al., 2011], with pupil dilation also mimicking the inferred LC online activity in man [Gabay et al., 2011]. A well-documented model for LC noradrenergic control of attention has emerged under the name of “adaptive gain”. This model proposes that noradrenergic neurons of the LC serve to increase activity contrast between certain cortical units to afford more downstream effect to some and less to others; this contrast increase is formally termed “gain” [Aston-Jones and Cohen, 2005]. Evidence for this model has emerged from behavioural task engagement and disengagement, evaluated in light of LC neuronal efferences to the orbitofrontal and anterior cingulate cortices (OFC and AFC respectively) [Aston-Jones and Cohen, 2005]; both of these structures being well-known for their role in behavioural control [Baxter and Croxson, 2013; Kerns, 2004]. The adaptive gain model has also found supporting evidence in humans, where global fluctuations in functional connectivity have been shown to correlate with task difficulty and task-effected pupil dilation [Eldar et al., 2013].

Pharmacological studies in humans have shown that the effects of the wakefulness-promoting drug [Engber et al., 1998] modafinil can be reversed by clonidine, presumably due to an LC mediated mechanism of action for modafinil [Hou et al., 2005]. A high-profile fMRI study published in the journal *Science* reiterated this hypothesis and identified an LC activity shift upon modafinil administration via functional imaging [Minzenberg et al., 2008]. The accuracy of the imaging has, however, subsequently been drawn into question, with commentators [Astafiev et al., 2010] pointing at discrepancies between the LC and the brain stem activation

coordinates reported. BOLD LC signals have been described as difficult to interpret when using response magnitudes as the main feature, and authors recommended a more time-course sensitive signal evaluation method [Astafiev et al., 2010]. Though no such recommendation was made, we believe applying pupil diameter as a regressor in a linear model specifying BOLD response would well complement previous studies.

Due to the wide-ranging processes which the LC is causally involved in controlling, we believe that its study is relevant for a broad number of neuropsychology subfields. Especially in liaison with the purported possibility of approximating LC activation via pupillometry [Gilzenrat et al., 2010; Murphy et al., 2011]; further research could be conducive to better techniques for monitoring and diagnosing affect, attention, and anxiety disorders, as well as gauging or predicting the effectiveness of drugs or therapy. Due to the portability [Bradley et al., 2010] and (comparatively) reduced costs of pupillometric equipment, we believe the well-informed use of pupillometry in neuropsychology would be of great benefit to personalized treatment and diagnosis. We also envision a utility herefor in the study of self-administered (recreational or therapeutic) drugs in natural settings - a research field where equipment portability is of utmost importance.

2.5 Focus

In our present study we are analysing behavioural, neuroimaging, and pupillometric data. To facilitate this integration of methods, we are also concentrating on the innovation and documentation of new paradigms and stimulus presentation and analysis software. In our study we explore:

- The viability of a novel feature-obfuscation algorithm as a baseline for established visual matching tasks.
- The viability of pupillometry study in the current optometry-fMRI set-up at the Central Institute of Mental Health.
- The time course of pupillometric data as modulated by task difficulty.
- The time course of pupillometric data as modulated by task type (emotion vs. pattern matching).
- The time course of pupillometric data as modulated by the emotional valence of stimulus images (happy vs. fearful).
- The covariance of Locus Coeruleus activation and pupil dilation during visual matching.

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Participants

Participants were recruited via flyers and advertisements pinned to information boards in multiple locations at the University of Mannheim and the University of Heidelberg. As part of this study, a total number of 12 participants have been tested; 4 male and 8 female. Participants were aged 18-29, and had no a priori documented psychiatric or neurologic conditions.

Participants were screened for fMRI testing and gave written informed consent in accordance with the ethical guidelines at the Central Institute of Mental Health.

3.1.1 Trial Procedure

Participants were invited for an appointment after having completed a questionnaire (see section 3.7). The appointment commenced with safety instructions and discussion of the information/consent forms. Participants were placed in the fMRI/eye tracking set-up where they completed the behavioural test documented in section 3.2 (after approximately 5 min of anatomical measurements and 17 min of an other behavioural test performed as part of a different study). Genetic material samples (detailed in section 3.8) were taken after approximately 45 min of time spent in the scanner.

3.2 Visual Matching Task

In our current study we are exploring neuronal function in visual emotional perception. Our behavioural task of choice to tap into these systems relies on visual recognition and subsequent matching of emotions and/or patterns. We call our paradigm a Hariri-style behavioural test,

in acknowledgement of the seminal implementations of a similar paradigm by Hariri and colleagues [Hariri et al., 2000, 2003].

The paradigm consists of a triangular arrangement of three faces - with the bottom two aligned horizontally and the upper face displaced vertically and equidistant from both bottom faces. The behavioural test prompts the participant to observe a certain feature (in our case emotion, or - as described in section 3.3.2 - pixel arrangement) of the top face, and to select of the bottom faces the one repeating that feature.

In our case bottom face selection was done via the arrow keys of a keyboard (in the preliminary experiments reported under section 4.4) and via a response box (in the fMRI trials reported under section 3.5). The participants received no sort of feedback after reacting to the individual items.

The images were continuously displayed independently of input for 5 s or 4.5 s (in the preliminary experiments), and for 4 s (in the fMRI trials). Inter-trial intervals - fixation periods - showed a dot (in the preliminary experiments) or a cross (in the fMRI experiments) and lasted for 2 s or around 4 s respectively.

The higher inter-trial interval duration for the fMRI experiments was chosen to accommodate for a jitter of one fMRI scan repetition time (TR, 2 s). Inter-trial intervals have been jittered around the value of 4 s with a maximum jitter amplitude of 2 s.

3.2.1 Trial Sequences

Trial sequences were computed to allow for event-related data analysis. For the fMRI trials we have employed fixed trial sequences to increase signal detection power. These trial sequences were calculated using the Optseq2 [Greve, 2002] software package, from a list with permitted and counterbalanced stimulus compositions computed by our Pystim [Christian, 2013d] script.

According to the stimulus compositions and trial sequences, each condition (easy emotion matching, difficult emotion matching, easy pattern matching, difficult pattern matching) is represented by 32 trials - in which all pictures depicting a strong emotion are used as a template: $8 \times \{\text{male; female}\} \times \{\text{happy; fearful}\}$. Thereby within each condition every picture is repeated thrice - once as the template, once as the target, and once as the distractor. An exception from this is that in difficult emotion matching trials - where we use images with a lower emotional concentration (see section 3.3.1) - the templates are still images from the higher emotion concentration set.

3.2.2 Visual Composition

In contrast to other formulations [Hariri et al., 2000, 2003] of the same paradigm (which keep all 3 stimuli equidistant), we have decided to adapt the positions of stimulus images to what we believe is a better fit for the human field of view. Simply aligning the midpoints of stimulus images to the vertices of an equilateral triangle presents some issues:

- Not accounting for the aspect ratio of the stimulus images lessens control over the shape and size of the resulting populated visual window (pVW).
- Horizontal and diagonal distances are not registered identically by human vision [Terry Bahill and Stark, 1975].

Figure 3.1: Perimetric map of the human field of view [Ruch and Fulton, 1960]. For measurement the head and eyes were fixed, with the fovea pointing at 0° on the cross-hairs. The white area affords binocular vision, the black area is completely outside the field of view.

We tackled the above by adapting the pVW to the normal human field of vision aspect ratio. To do so, we took the outermost non-neutral pixels (rather than the centers of the stimulus images) and used these as pVW delimiters in deciding where to position our images.

For the following distance specifications we have defined the unit “u” as the height of our stimulus images. Seeing as our stimulus images have a fixed aspect ratio their width is thus consistently $\frac{3}{4}$ u.

The static human field of view has a complex shape modulated amongst others by facial features (as seen in figure 3.1). If the outermost light paths fitting figure 3.1 were to be circumscribed by a planar mask in the shape of the rectangle, its height would span approximately 130° and its width 180° . This gives the rectangular fit for the field of view a width-to-height ratio of $0.72(2)$. Given this information - and for numerical convenience - we have chosen to position the midpoints of our stimulus images as follows:

- The distance between the two lower image midpoints is 2 u.
- The vertical offset of the top image midpoint from the horizontal line connecting the bottom image midpoints is 1 u

This gives our pVW a total height of $2u$ and a total width of $\frac{11}{4}u$. The resulting width-to-height ratio of $0.(72)$ was deemed a sufficiently close match for the afore mentioned human field of view (as approximated by a rectangle). We thus have reason to believe that our stimulus item distribution is superior to the one implemented by Hariri and colleagues, and we encourage further users of Hariri-style paradigms to consider our observations.

In addition to field of view shape, saccades are an other parameter which offers valuable information on the accuracy and speed with which the eyes track distance (e.g. across a monitor). We are aware that our simplified approximation still does not quantitatively account for vertical saccades being slower [Terry Bahill and Stark, 1975] and less accurate [Collewijn et al., 1988] than horizontal saccades, nor for the fact that upward saccades tend to undershoot while downward saccades tend to overshoot [Collewijn et al., 1988]; however, integrating accurate metrics for these kinetics and determining their relevance for Hariri-style paradigms differs in focus from and far exceeds the scope of our current study.

Our resulting pVW was scaled to fit the available display field of the monitor and tilted mirror set-up in our MRI scanner (more on this in section 3.4.1). The dimensions (specified in degrees of visual angle) are proportional to the ones mentioned above, scaled for $u = 4.24^\circ$. The midpoint of the pVW (at $0.5u$ downward from the midpoint of the top image) was aligned to the midpoint of the monitor. A picture of this visual set-up can be seen in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Sample image from the emotional face matching trials in our Hariri-style behavioural task.

3.3 Stimulus Images

3.3.1 Emotional Faces

The emotional face stimuli required by our visual matching task (see section 3.2) have been sourced from the NimStim set of facial expressions [Tottenham et al., 2009]. We have decided to use different emotion intensities in order to better describe step-wise effects of emotion perception and/or emotion recognition for either pupil dilation time courses, brain activation, reaction times - or interactions thereof.

Our emotion intensities of choice are 40 % and 100 % - these being referred to as weak (“hard” in the sense of recognition) and strong (“easy” in the sense of recognition) emotion images respectively. The semi-quantitative measure of emotion (in percent) stems from the image morphing used to obtain these images - 40 % happy images are thus a 4:6 linear combination of 0 % happy (i.e. neutral) and 100 % happy eigenfaces [Zhang and Turk, 2008] respectively.

The choice of 40 % was made to obtain the highest possible activation variance both in brain areas presenting discrete (amygdala) or continuous (superior temporal sulcus) sensitivity to increasing emotional concentrations [Harris et al., 2012]. Our images comprise 8 male and 8 female faces, displaying happiness and fear, in the two concentrations mentioned above.

3.3.2 Scrambled Images

In order to define a pattern recognition (baseline) condition we have decided to use trials in which visual input consists of the same pixels as in the emotional trials. This is especially relevant to pupillometry, for which we would like to ensure condition-independent luminosity.

To disentangle pattern identification from semantic (emotion) processing we decided to use “scrambled” images - in which pixels from the emotional faces are permuted so as to obfuscate emotional expressions and facial features. The recognition trials would thus entail matching identical permutations of the same picture. For these trials the template and target are the exact same image. The distractor (i.e. the non-target image) is a different permutation of the pixels which constitute the source image (the image which template/target were also computed from).

Corresponding to the emotion recognition trials, we include two sets of scrambled image trials: “easy” and “difficult”. These are to act as baselines for easy and difficult emotion recognition trials respectively. Recognition difficulty of the scrambled image trials should scale proportion-

ally with that of the easy and difficult emotion recognition trials (detailed under section 3.3.1). To achieve this, scrambling has to be progressively complex. We assume that scrambling of images via progressively smaller sub-sections (further referred to as “clusters”) makes the images progressively more difficult to identify and match to other copies. This rationale determined the nature of our scrambling algorithms (detailed below) and was also experimentally validated in preliminary trials (as described in section 4.5).

Based on the preliminary results to be detailed in section 4.4 we have decided to use composite (kernel *and* cluster based) scrambling for our experiment. The scrambling kernel was constant at 6 px (following considerations explained in sections 4.3.3.2) and “hard” recognition trials had a scrambling cluster size of 10 px while “easy” trials had a scrambling cluster of 22 px (following preliminary experiment results described in section 4.5.2). The quality of this baseline is assessed under section 4.5.1.

Scrambling was done via Pyxrand [Christian, 2013e], a Python script written for the purpose of this thesis and openly published on GitHub. The script provides both cluster-based and kernel-based scrambling:

3.3.2.1 Cluster-Based Scrambling

The Cluster-Based Scrambling functionality recognises the face region of interest (ROI) by thresholding pixel lines by the number of unique values. It then divides the face ROI in square clusters of predefined sizes. The clusters then get permuted and rewritten in-place on the image - this is done via the `montage2d` function (of the `scikit-image` python package), which was adapted for this purpose as part of this thesis and contributed to the package for the benefit of the scientific community. Finally, the script fills the image background (outside of the ROI) with homogeneous values.

3.3.2.2 Kernel-Based Scrambling

The Kernel-Based scrambling variant is performed by remapping every pixel of the image via the `geometric_transform` function provided by the SciPy ecosystem [Jones et al., 2001–present; Oliphant, 2007]. New positions are computed via a function which adds a random integer in the $[-K; K]$ (K being the scrambling kernel integer) interval to both the X and Y coordinates of the said pixel. Effectively, this redistributes each pixel in an area of $[-K; K]$ along each axis around its original position with a standard deviation (σ) of $\approx 0.96K$ (as calculated in figure 7.1).

3.4 Occulometry

As part of our experiments we have measured oculometric parameters of our participants during behavioural trials performed inside the MRI scanner. Oculometric data was captured via an infra-red SemoMotoric Instruments (SMI) “TVIEW X™ MRI-LR” 60 Hz fMRI-compatible eye tracker. The light source needed to afford signal for the eye-tracking camera is built-in and shines infra-red light. This avoids triggering the pupillary light reflex [Ellis, 1981] and distorting the pupil diameter data.

3.4.1 Eye Tracking

More accurately, we are performing “gaze tracking” rather than “eye tracking”, as the system measures the gaze coordinates rather than eye-in-head angles. We use “eye tracking” as a general term for both measurements, keeping with the trend in both industry specifications [Bojko, 2006] as well as peer-reviewed publications [Kirk et al., 2013].

3.4.1.1 Data Acquisition

Gaze coordinates are calculated by the firmware provided with our eye tracker, based on the position of the corneal light source reflection relative to the pupil. As our stimulus presentation does not yet incorporate a drift correction mechanism, our eye-tracking data is subject to gross movement artefacts.

3.4.2 Pupillometry

3.4.2.1 Data Acquisition

From the data provided by the aforementioned hardware we are separately extracting the pupil diameter. The pupil is identified by the firmware of our eye tracker via the contrast between pupil (dark) and iris (bright under infra-red light, regardless of eye color) Pupil area is approximated by the firmware via an edge detection algorithm with a perimeter-to-area ratio constraint. (keeping the detected area as close as possible to a circular form).

3.4.2.2 Data Analysis

Pupillometric data is analysed and plotted via the specialized faceOM script suite [Christian, 2013a].

Our data is slightly distorted due to a number of factors: most prominently subjects' eyelids covering parts of the pupils; or dark make-up of some female participants being registered as pupil area. These distortions are not critical for gaze point calculation (as long as they remain constant over the course of calibration and measurement); but they do interfere non-linearly with the firmware-calculated pupil area (pupil area lost to eyelid coverage, for instance, scales quite complexly with overlap distance - see figure 7.3). To avoid such complex data-reconstruction algorithms we are considering using the pupil horizontal diameter as a reference measure for the pupil dilation response in lieu of the actual area. These considerations are further addressed based on experimental results under section 5.2.

3.5 Functional MRI

In the present study we are using BOLD response data obtained via fMRI as a proxy for neuronal activation. This data was acquired over a 3 T Siemens "TIM Trio" MRI scanner at the Central Institute of Mental Health in Mannheim.

3.5.1 Data Acquisition

176 anatomical slices were acquired in the sagittal plane via a T1-MPRAGE sequence [Brant-Zawadzki et al., 1992], with a repetition time (TR) of 1.57 s, an echo time of 2.7 ms, and a flip angle of 15°. The slice thickness and the X and Y-axis resolution (relative to the acquisition plane) of the tomographic data were 1 mm (1 mm³ voxel size).

Functional data was acquired via T2* weighted echo-planar imaging (T2* EPI), with a repetition time (TR) of 2 s, an echo time of 30 ms, and a flip angle of 80°. A total of 33 transversal slices were acquired in descending (dorsocaudal) order, at a slice thickness of 3 mm, and an X and Y-axis resolution of again 3 mm (27 mm³ voxel size).

3.5.2 Data Processing

The resulting fMRI data in `.dcm` (DICOM) format was converted to the more convenient `.nii` (NIfTI) via the MRIconvert [Smith, 2010] software package. Unless otherwise specified, all subsequent NIfTI file processing and analysis was performed via SPM8 [Wellcome Trust Centre for Neuroimaging] - a MATLAB[®]-based brain imaging analysis suite.

Further preprocessing steps have been done in accordance with the established guidelines of the group, and are documented (in simplified form) as part of the faceOM script suite [Christian,

2013a] - which was written for the purpose of this thesis and openly published for the benefit of researchers pursuing similar analysis.

Slice timing correction was done according to the EPI sequence - in descending order of slices, non-interlaced, and with the 17th slice (the middle slice) as the reference. Normalization of the data was achieved by coregistration of the EPI to the anatomical scan, segmentation of the anatomical scan, coregistration to the standard MNI (Montreal Neurological Institute) template, and subsequent mapping of the EPI to these parameters. Data was realigned to the mean image, and smoothing was done with a $6 \times 6 \times 6$ mm full width half maximum kernel.

Figure 3.3: Mask for the LC based on MNI coordinates extracted from in-vivo MRI localization [Keren et al., 2009].

The mask was smoothed and the dynamic range remapped to $[-1;1]$.

Data was analysed by a first-level computation of per-participant contrasts, and a subsequent second-level statistical analysis of these contrasts, resulting in an activation probability map. First level analyses used movement regressors as regressors of no interest, and per-condition lists of trial onsets as regressors of interest. The conditions which we have compared are:

- Hard vs. easy trials (integrating both emotion and pattern matching)
- Easy emotion matching trials vs. easy pattern matching trials
- Hard emotion matching trials vs. hard pattern matching trials
- Hard emotion matching trials vs. easy emotion matching trials.

Additionally, pupil diameter time course data obtained from infra-red pupillometry (see section 3.4.2) was down-sampled to a rate of 0.5 Hz (to match the functional TR) and used as a signal regressor. As it is yet unclear what temporal relationship the pupil dilation response and LC activation have in humans, we implement this kind of regressor in a series of different variations:

- Raw pupil dilation time course
- Pupil dilation time course convolved with the hemodynamic response function (HRF)

- Numerical first differential of the pupil dilation time course
- Numerical first differential convolved with the hemodynamic response function (HRF)

The numerical first derivative (first differential) of the raw pupil area time course was computed by the faceOM script suite via the `DataFrame.diff()` function of the Pandas [PyData Development, 2008–present] library. The regressors were convoluted with the haemodynamic response function (HRF) via SPM8.

The second-level (significance determining) analysis step was done both with and without a locus coeruleus mask. We used a mask drawn for the purpose of this thesis in the MARINA program [Walter et al., 2003] and based on in-vivo magnetic resonance localization of the LC available in peer-reviewed literature [Keren et al., 2009]. Three representative cross sections of our mask are presented in figure 3.3

Coordinates of non-ROI (region of interest) brain activation clusters were assigned anatomical descriptions based on the Wake Forest University (WFU) PickAtlas [Maldjian et al., 2003]; and the anatomical descriptions are given as International Consortium for Brain Mapping (ICBM) labels. In cases where the coordinates exceed the bounds of the ICBM we convert them to Talairach coordinates and fall back to the Talairach atlas labelling. Unless otherwise specified all coordinates are given in Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) standard space.

3.6 Statistical Analysis

For the analysis of our data we have implemented a number of statistic methods from different software packages. Our choice of methods took into account transparency and reproducibility, and we have thus - whenever possible - avoided closed-source and/or graphical user interface based software (such as for example MATLAB[®] or SPSS[®]), and have published our data analysis scripts in full on-line. Many of the statistical analysis functions are called at compile time from the L^AT_EX code of this document, meaning that many of our statistical results are live.

For ease of overview we have compiled a short index with explicit naming and descriptions of our statistical analysis tools. The methods detailed hereafter are referred to in further sections of this document simply by their subsection names.

3.6.1 Paired T-Test

The t-test is a method used to test the null hypothesis that the population means of two compared sample groups are equal. The most frequently reported resulting measure of the test (the p -value) represents the probability of the presented data being observed if the null hypothesis is true. The t-test makes a small series of assumptions, among which is the independence of data points and the normal distribution of data.

Our experiments mainly rely on testing the same population on various conditions. To adapt the t-test to this constraint (where data points are no longer independent) we use the paired sample t-test (also known as a related sample t-tests). We implement this statistical method via the `scipy.stats.mstats.ttest_rel` function of the SciPy ecosystem [Jones et al., 2001–present; Oliphant, 2007].

In order to avoid inflating our significance, we are testing per-participant means instead of raw data points - unless specified otherwise. This also affords the advantage of averting undocumented violations of the normal distribution assumption of the t-test - since means of even non-normally distributed populations tend to be normally distributed. Additionally, unless otherwise specified, we are conducting two-tailed t-tests, as we are trying to minimize a priori assumptions in the explorative context of our study.

3.6.2 Standard Error of the Mean

Confusion around appropriate usage of the standard deviation (SD) and standard error of the mean (SEM) is a significant quality deficit and cause of imprecision in modern research [Nagele, 2003]. SD is a measure of single data point variability and tends to be constant over increasing sample size, whereas SEM is a measure of the data sample mean reliability and tends to decrease as the sample size increases [Altman and Bland, 2005; Streiner, 1996].

As we are in more cases concerned with per-category means than data point variability, our error bars of choice represent the SEM by default. Cases in which graphical depiction of the SD is helpful in understanding the data at hand are described accordingly and explicitly.

In our purpose-built scripts, faceRT [Christian, 2013b] and faceOM [Christian, 2013a], we use the `scipy.stats.sem` and `numpy.std` functions of the SciPy ecosystem [Jones et al., 2001–present; Oliphant, 2007] - for the standard error of the mean and standard deviation respectively.

3.6.3 ANOVA

ANOVA, the so-called analysis of variance, is a very popular set of statistical methods in psychology and related fields. Formally, ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that the population means of multiple groups are equal.

The method, however, has a series of limitations:

- ANOVA provides no information as to the group whose mean is outside the range of other groups, nor does it indicate whether this is one group or a number of groups.
- ANOVA does not deal well with missing measurements (which motivates scientists to perform ANOVA on means rather than on raw data points - and thus discard valuable information) [Gueorguieva and Krystal, 2004].
- The assumptions made by ANOVA - independence of observations, normal distribution of residuals, and homoscedasticity [Anderson et al., 1996] - are likely to be violated due to autocorrelation whenever using raw data points.

Overall, statisticians involved in biology and psychology recommend against ANOVA and point to mixed models (see section 3.6.4) as a substitute [Baayen et al., 2008; Gueorguieva and Krystal, 2004]. In light of these recommendations we are only using ANOVA in cases where raw data point sets represent per-participant or binned values (such as in questionnaires, or in error rate analyses - as seen under section 4.4.1).

In those cases where we do choose to resort to ANOVA, we have to consider that the standard one-way ANOVA assumes all data points are independent. For our applications - where we are testing the same sample of participants over a number of conditions - the appropriate variation of ANOVA would be the repeated measure ANOVA [Gueorguieva and Krystal, 2004]. Our ANOVA function of choice is `stats::aov` [Chambers et al., 1992] from the R statistical environment [R Core Team, 2013].

3.6.4 Mixed Models

Current literature [Baayen et al., 2008] recommends mixed models over ANOVA's standard linear model in order to describe the effect of multiple experimental conditions on measurements.

We fit mixed models to our data via the `lme4::lmer` [Bates, 2005, 2007] R function. This function - though one of the most powerful current tools for mixed modelling - fails to provide p -values. The author has justified this [Bates, 2006], and generally recommended against

using p -values with such models. In spite of this recommendation, we hold that p -values are a stringent standard in quantifying the reliability of scientific observations - and are using the alternate `nlme::lme` [Pinheiro et al., 2013] function whenever we believe p -values are needed.

We are using these functions in many instances to compute mixed models *live* in this document. For this purpose we are using the `interstats` [Christian, 2013c] software package as a wrapper. This software was written for the purpose of this thesis and openly published on GitHub [GitHub Inc., 2008–present].

3.6.5 Pearson’s r

We use “Pearson’s r ” for the quantitative description of variable dependence - in cases where we believe this dependence can be reasonably approximated by linear correlation. Pearson’s r is a century-old method with widespread use in the empirical sciences [Stigler, 1989]. It is however noteworthy that it is only meaningful for linear correlations (or nonlinear correlations with significant linear components).

To test for this statistical measure we are using the `scipy.stats.pearsonr` function from the Scipy ecosystem [Jones et al., 2001–present; Oliphant, 2007]. To determine the linear equation of regression lines we use the least-squares solution of the linear matrix equation of our measurement vectors. This is performed by the `numpy.linalg.lstsq` function provided by the Scipy suite.

3.7 Questionnaires

We have decided to complement our studies with a series of validated and widely used questionnaires. These tests could provide valuable insight into the interplay between psychotypes on one side and behavioural parameters or their neurophysiological underpinnings on the other. For test presentation we have decided on a web-based approach, for which we have used a web-enabled version of the free and open source (FOSS) software `testMaker` [Hartweg et al., 2013].

The choice of tests was based on both general relevance to the host group’s research, and specific relevance to emotional perception. According to these criteria, we have compiled a selection of 8 questionnaires:

- The Autism Spectrum Quotient questionnaire (**AQ**) [Baron-Cohen et al., 2001]

- The World Health Organization Adult ADHD Self-Report Scale (**ASRS**) [Kessler et al., 2005]
- The 1996 revised Beck Depression Inventory (**BDI2**) [Beck et al., 1996]
- The short version of the Borderline Symptoms List (**BSL23**) [Bohus et al., 2009]
- The Empathizing Quotient questionnaire (**EQ**) [Baron-Cohen and Wheelwright, 2004]
- The Systemizing Quotient questionnaire (**SQ**) [Baron-Cohen et al., 2003]
- The Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (**ERQ**) [Gross and John, 2003]
- The Schizotypal Personality Questionnaire (**SPQ**) [Raine, 1991]

The questionnaires were administered in German language, and translated and validated versions were provided by the test databases of the Central Institute of Mental Health. Translation references are as follows:

- **AQ** - Translated by C.M. Freitag, Homburg
- **ASRS** - Translated by Dr. P. Kirsch, JLU Gießen 2005
- **BDI2** - Translated by Pearson Assessment & Information GmbH (Frankfurt/M. 2010)
- **BSL23** - Translated at the Department of Psychosomatic Medicine and Psychotherapy, Central Institute of Mental Health.
- **EQ** - Translated by Dipl.-Psych. Jörn de Haen
- **SQ** - Translated by Dipl.-Psych. Jörn de Haen
- **ERQ** - Translated by Brigit Abler and Henrik Kessler [Abler and Kessler, 2009]
- **SPQ** - Translated by Klein, Andersen, and Jahn [Klein et al., 1997]

The questionnaires were evaluated with `questioPy` [Christian, 2013f], a Python script written for the purpose of this thesis and openly published on GitHub [GitHub Inc., 2008–present].

3.8 Genetic Material Samples

We have harvested mouth epithelial cells from our participants for prospective genotyping. The cells were obtained as a saliva sample collected via an Oragene[®]-DNA “Self-Collection Kit OG-500” (DNA Genotek Inc. Ottawa, Ontario, Canada).

The resulting suspensions are stored at room temperature (15 °C to 30 °C) and shall be genotyped whenever the participant sample reaches an adequate size for genetic testing (62 participants). The choice to resort to saliva rather than whole-blood lymphoblast testing was made in light of cost and safety considerations, though we are aware of the method's limited reliability [Philibert et al., 2008].

Chapter 4

Excursus: Preliminary Experiments

4.1 Background

Our visual matching task (as described in detail under section 3.2) relies on both emotion and pattern recognition. As luminosity variations could greatly disturb our pupillary measurements, we need equally luminous images in all conditions. In this thesis we are employing a novel feature-obfuscation algorithm, Pyxrand [Christian, 2013e], which allows us to process the same images we use for emotion recognition and use them as pattern recognition templates - the algorithm is more accurately described under section 3.3.2.

In order to make better informed decisions in our methods section (chapter 3) we are performing a series of preliminary experiments whereby we determine how various parameters of our image processing script impact reaction times and error rates.

4.2 Focus

The parameters whose effect on reaction times and error rates we shall test are the following:

- Scrambling type (our script provides both cluster-based and kernel-based scrambling, functions which we explicitly detail under section 3.3.2).
- Scrambling resolution.

The information which we try to extract from combinations of the above is:

- What scrambling kind and resolution provide for equally fast performance in pattern recognition trials as in our easy and hard emotion recognition trials (see section 3.3.1 for information on our emotional images).
- What scrambling kind and resolution provide for equally accurate performance in pattern recognition trials as in our easy and hard emotion recognition trials.

4.3 Methods

4.3.1 Participants

Participants were recruited from staff at the Central Institute of Mental Health, and students of the Universities of Mannheim and Heidelberg. Since these are preparatory trials we opted for merely around 7 participants per run. Participants are identified in the study by a 2-letter code, and a subset of them have participated in multiple runs of our preliminary trials. It should be noted that runs are therefore not well suited for direct comparison or for binning; but they do offer a good predictor for expected variability in reaction times.

4.3.2 Visual Matching Task

For stimulus presentation and data acquisition in these experiments we used faceRT [Christian, 2013b], a Python script written for the purpose of this thesis and openly published on GitHub [GitHub Inc., 2008–present]. Our script uses the PsychoPy suite [Peirce, 2008] for specialized, high-precision stimulus rendering and timing.

The behavioural test was done in accordance with the guidelines for our main experiment run (specified under section 3.2). We have varied some of the parameters over our preliminary trials:

4.3.2.1 Simple Cluster-Based Scrambling

The stimulus presentation protocol used for these trials is revision `ce2b3a8f30` of the faceRT [Christian, 2013b] script suite. Stimuli were presented fully randomized per-participant, and stimulus sequences were compiled manually, following the listed requirements:

- Each condition should have 10 corresponding trials (conditions are: emotion {happy; afraid} × emotion intensity {40%; 100%}; and emotion {happy; afraid} × scrambling {6; 10; 14; 18; 22; 26}) - yielding a total of 160 trials.

- The same person's face (even with a different emotion) should not appear more than once in one slide.
- Each face picture should appear no more than 3 times in the entire experiment.

To better determine the appropriate response window duration for further trials, we have decided on a conservative duration of 5 s.

4.3.2.2 Composite Kernel-and-Cluster-Based Scrambling

Here the stimulus sequence was re-written in a more automated and reliable manner. The automation was done via the sequence-calculation software, Pystim [Christian, 2013d] - a Python script written for the purpose of this thesis and openly published on GitHub. The requirements followed and met by the script are:

- Each emotional picture should be presented once as the template (emotion defining) figure, once as a target, and once as a distractor.
- Trial repeat number for each scrambling severity and emotional concentration should be equal
- The same person's face (even with a different emotion) should not appear more than once in any one emotion-recognition trial.

The decision to show all emotional images an equal number of times and present each one as the template lead to a total increase of the trial count ($8 \text{ faces} \times 2 \text{ genders} \times 2 \text{ emotions} \times 2 \text{ intensities}$ *plus* $8 \text{ faces} \times 2 \text{ genders} \times 2 \text{ emotions} \times 6 \text{ intensities}$ yields 256 trials as opposed to the 160 resulting from the stimulus sequence in section 4.3.2.1). To limit fatigue experienced by our participants we have decided to only test 5 scrambling cell steps at a time (reducing the trial number to 224).

Additionally, to constrain test duration and relieve fatigue for our participants we have decided to provide a response window of 4 s. This somewhat undershoots the recommended value from section 4.4.1. In light of the necessity to reduce test duration and in light of acquisition time considerations further detailed in section 3.5, we have - however - decided that this is a fair trade-off.

4.3.3 Stimulus Images

4.3.3.1 Simple Cluster-Based Scrambling

In a first set of trials we have scrambled images with scrambling clusters of sizes starting at 6 px and progressing to 26 px in 4 px steps.

4.3.3.2 Composite Kernel-and-Cluster-Based Scrambling

As the previous set-up of preliminary experiments proved unsatisfactory due to ectopic eye visibility (which is known to elicit fearful emotional reactions [Whalen, 2004] that could well disrupt our brain imaging baseline), we decided to further obfuscate facial features. This was done by kernel-scrambling the images (as detailed in section 3.3.2.2) before applying the same cluster-based scrambling as in the experiments mentioned above. Such a preparation of the images renders all features with a horizontal and/or vertical spatial frequency above $\frac{1}{\sigma_K}$ (where σ_K is the pixel redistribution standard deviation demonstratively calculated in figure 7.1) arguably unrecognisable.

The transition from the black of the pupil over the iris to the white of the cornea in our stimulus images averages around 8 px (based on manual analysis). We therefore experimented with a series of kernel-based scrambling steps around that value.

We found that for smaller scrambling kernels, the spatial frequency low-pass cut-off was too low (as seen in in figures 4.1a and 4.1b where the eyes are still visible). We also found that for the 8 px scrambling kernel, the subsequent cluster-based scrambling includes very many clusters with predominantly background patches (as seen in figure 4.1d). This happens because, as the scrambling kernel becomes larger, face-pixels diffuse further into the background forming a sparsely populated halo which still has to be included to preserve pixel consistency.

For the 6 px kernel we found that the eyes were still recognisable in the picture which had not yet undergone cluster-based scrambling, but became unrecognisable after cluster-based scrambling. The recognition of the eyes in the first image of figure 4.1c relies on contextual information from other low-frequency features. When the image is scrambled on a cluster basis, a second high-pass cut-off takes place - after which only features with a vertical and/or horizontal spatial frequency strictly above $\frac{1}{26\text{px}}$ (26 px being the cluster height and width) can be distinguished. With the contextual information from other features such as brows and nose gone, the pupil, the iris, and adjacent portions of the eyelids only look like a dark blob. Based on these tests we have decided to use faces pre-scrambled with a kernel of 6 px for the second round of reaction time testing.

Figure 4.1: Kernel-based scrambling of faces followed by composite (kernel-based and then cluster-based) scrambling of the same faces. The kernels are ascending in size; images were prepared via Pyxrand[Christian, 2013e] (revision 1eb1f7cd65).

4.3.4 Data Post-Processing

Our data analysis script handles system flaws in reaction time recording (whereby negative reaction times are printed) by replacing the value with the median of the category of interest which the trial is part of. These categories are defined by the nature of the presented stimulus, and are: “emotional easy”, “emotional hard”, and “scrambled X” with X being any of the scrambling cluster sizes tested in each run of the experiment. It should be noted that such errors appear only very rarely (at most twice in a measurement), so this slight manipulation via the most outlier-resistant predictor should impact the data in no other way than assuring its viability for statistical methods requiring full datasets.

4.4 Results

In the following experiments we examine reaction times and error rates for the recognition of progressively scrambled images in comparison to the recognition of our two emotional concentrations. The reaction time figures which we present include both per-participant and population sample bar plots (the latter marked as “ALL”).

4.4.1 Cluster-Based Scrambling

For the results presented in figure 4.2 we have used a simple cluster-based scrambling algorithm and a hand-written balanced stimulus sequence (detailed in sections 4.3.3 and 4.3.2.1).

Figure 4.2 shows that reaction times for the difficult emotion recognition condition are significantly different from (one-tailed related sample t-test p -value of 2.6×10^{-12}), and higher than for the easy condition. The results also indicate the presence of a downward trend in reaction times over increasing scrambling cluster sizes. Additionally we see the emergence of a plateau-phase over higher scrambling cluster sizes.

To test the validity of our tentative interpretation regarding a plateau phase, we have fitted a mixed model to the reaction times of pattern recognition trials. The model presented in table 4.1 supports this interpretation by showing that:

- There is a negative progression among the first three factors, with all factor values lying outside of the confidence intervals of all others.
- For the subsequent 4 factors there is no obvious trend, with all factor values lying within each other’s confidence intervals.

Figure 4.2: Reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed only with a scrambling cluster of the sizes indicated in the graphic (sizes given in pixels). Reaction times for non-response trials were counted as 5 s. The error bars represent the standard deviation.

Model 1	
(Intercept)	2.48 [2.23; 2.73]*
CoI:scrambling-10	-0.45 [-0.60; -0.30]*
CoI:scrambling-14	-0.68 [-0.83; -0.53]*
CoI:scrambling-18	-0.68 [-0.83; -0.53]*
CoI:scrambling-22	-0.64 [-0.79; -0.49]*
CoI:scrambling-26	-0.77 [-0.92; -0.62]*
Num. obs.	840
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.07
Variance: Residual	0.41

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 4.1: Mixed model fitted to the raw data depicted in figure 4.2. Our factors are the conditions of interest (CoI), excluding the emotion recognition trials. The model chooses the first factor (scrambling-06) as the base intercept. Note the downwards trend for the first 3 factors and that the last 4 factors' values lie within each other's confidence intervals.

As we can see in table 4.2 pattern recognition of figures produced with a 6 px scrambling cluster recommends itself as the least unlikely (to keep with accurate terminology of the hypothesis testing we are performing) condition to share an equivalent baseline with difficult emotion recognition. Similarly, it is pattern recognition of images processed with a 22 px scrambling cluster which we choose as our best-guess reaction time equivalent for easy emotion recognition.

Conditions of interest	Proposed best estimators (scrambling cluster sizes in px)					
	6	10	14	18	22	26
emotion-easy	2.1×10^{-3}	6.4×10^{-2}	6.7×10^{-1}	7.6×10^{-1}	9.5×10^{-1}	2.3×10^{-1}
emotion-hard	6.0×10^{-1}	1.3×10^{-1}	1.6×10^{-2}	3.6×10^{-2}	2.3×10^{-2}	1.5×10^{-2}

Table 4.2: Two-tailed paired sample t-test p -values for the data in figure 4.2; testing the probability of our measured observations if the compared conditions share the same mean. Note that - though unorthodox - this test does not lose accuracy due to multiple comparisons. As we are looking for the group least likely to reject the null hypothesis, multiple comparison actually makes the test more stringent.

In addition to the reaction time per-category analysis, we attempted to gauge the maximal window for reaction times which we should provide in further experiments. For this analysis we have selectively looked at reaction times for images processed with 0 px, 6 px, and 22 px scrambling clusters (due to considerations detailed above and documented in table 4.2).

Figure 4.3: Histogram of reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed only with a scrambling cluster. Missed targets have not been counted. For this graphic we have only indexed the 0, 6, 22 pixel scrambling cluster trials.

Figure 4.3 shows the reaction time distribution for the said subset of trials. The mean value (μ) for the reaction times is approximately 2.11 s, and the standard deviation (σ) of the fitted normal distribution is approximately 0.8 s. Based on the three-sigma rule (see figure 7.2 for a general expression) we have decided that a reaction time cut-off of 4.51 s should not statistically distort our data.

We have also tried to analyse the error rates in our Hariri-style matching task in order to extract more information on the appropriateness of our proposed baselines. The results herefor are presented in figure 4.4. The data presented therein shows a constant null error rate for easy emotion recognition.

Figure 4.4: Error rates for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed only with a scrambling cluster of the sizes indicated in the graphic (sizes given in pixels). The error bars represent the standard deviation. Bar-plots with zero-height have been slightly indented for better visibility.

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	6	0.01	0.00		
CoI	7	0.02	0.00	1.93	0.0887
Residuals1	42	0.06	0.00		

Table 4.3: One-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 4.4. The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability of observed results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

To test whether error rates for this one condition are indeed significantly different we have performed an ANOVA (see table 4.3). The value lies considerably above the popular signifi-

cance threshold of $p < 0.05$, indicating that the data does not support our tentative interpretation.

4.4.2 Composite (Kernel-and-Cluster-Based) Scrambling

Based on the results presented in section 4.4.1 we have performed additional experiments using a series of improved method choices (detailed in sections 4.3.3.2 and 4.3.2.2).

We have re-run experiments with kernel-and-cluster scrambled images a number of times. This was based on progressively noticing parameters in need of adjustment so as to create a most faithful emulation of the in-scanner visual experience. For the sake of brevity, we will only discuss the results of our final and most faithful emulation here in this section. Data from the previous runs is appended for the sake of completion under section 7.1.

Figure 4.5: Reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed with composite cluster and kernel based scrambling, with a constant kernel of 6 px and clusters of the sizes indicated in the graphic (sizes given in pixels). Reaction times for non-response trials were counted as 5 s. The light error bars represent the standard deviation, while the dark bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 4.5 presents the the data from the final preliminary experiment run - which best approximates the visual input participants will be receiving in the fMRI trials, and which we trust above all others as an appropriate guideline for further experimental choices. Here we present the standard deviation graphically alongside the standard error of the mean to better illustrate the true variability of our reaction times. An obvious feature of this graphic is the

disappearance of the plateau phase, which we have previously observed; this is only partly corroborated by other test runs, as seen in supplementary figures 7.4 and 7.5).

We have tried to determine the best-guess equivalent for our categories of interest - in terms of reaction times - using a t-test p -value listing (see table 4.4). Our results indicate that pattern recognition of figures produced with a 11 px scrambling cluster is the least unlikely condition to share an equivalent baseline with difficult emotion recognition. Similarly, it is pattern recognition of images processed with a 23 px scrambling cluster which is the best-guess reaction time equivalent for easy emotion recognition.

Conditions of interest	Proposed best estimators (scrambling cluster sizes in px)				
	11	15	19	23	27
emotion-easy	6.6×10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-1}	4.3×10^{-1}	9.5×10^{-1}	8.0×10^{-1}
emotion-hard	6.2×10^{-1}	4.5×10^{-1}	6.0×10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-2}	3.1×10^{-3}

Table 4.4: Table of two-tailed paired sample t-test p -values for the data in figure 4.5, testing the probability of our observations if the compared conditions share the same mean. Note that - though unorthodox - this test does not lose accuracy due to multiple comparisons. As we are looking for the group least likely to reject the null hypothesis, multiple comparison actually makes the test more stringent.

Figure 4.6: Error rates for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed with composite cluster and kernel based scrambling, with a constant kernel of 6 px and clusters of the sizes indicated in the graphic (sizes given in pixels). The error bars represent the standard deviation. Bar-plots with zero-height have been slightly indented for better visibility.

To re-examine potential weaknesses of our baseline concept (related to error rate distribution

and further discussed in section 4.4.1), we have also analysed error rates for this last and methodologically most faithful preliminary experiment run. Figure 4.6 presents a slightly divergent picture from what we have seen in figure 4.4. For one thing, the easy emotion recognition condition no longer has a null error rate. This time, however, there is a significant error rate divergence for one of our conditions compared to all of the others (as seen in figure 4.6, and verified in table 4.5).

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	6	0.02	0.00		
CoI	6	0.03	0.00	3.45	0.0085
Residuals1	36	0.05	0.00		

Table 4.5: One-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 4.6. The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability of observed results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

We also analyse whether our reaction time window could constrain our data. In figure 4.7 we see that reaction times seem to fade approximately 0.5s before our cut-off, and the fitted normal distribution does not indicate expected results beyond that point.

Figure 4.7: Histogram of reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed with a scrambling kernel of 6 px and with scrambling cluster. Missed targets have not been counted. For this graphic we have only indexed the 0, 11, 23 pixel scrambling cluster trials.

4.5 Discussion

4.5.1 Final Model Quality Assessment

We have decided to fit a mixed model to both the reaction times and error rates of our last-run data in order to check the quality of the baseline we have proposed as the best-guess solution based on the data detailed above. For this model we are defining “scrambling” and “difficulty” as our factors of interest (independent variables). Easy emotion recognition and its corresponding pattern recognition variant (6 px kernel- and 23 px cluster-scrambled) are defined as easy, while hard emotion recognition and its corresponding pattern recognition variant (6 px kernel- and 11 px cluster-scrambled) are defined as hard.

For our ideal baseline we would be expecting a null value for the scrambling factor and a positive value for the difficulty factor in the reaction time model. In the error rate model we would be expecting a null value for the scrambling factor and either a null or positive value for the difficulty factor.

Tables 4.6 and 4.7, provide a succinct and reliable validation for our proposed baseline model.

Table 4.6 recommends the choice of scrambling as a suitable baseline creation method for our task. The factor determined for this dimension is null, meaning that scrambling does not compromise the behavioural equivalence of emotional testing and baseline trials. Difficulty does also not seem to impact the error rate, which we consider fortunate, though a higher error rate for difficult trials would also have been acceptable. The interaction effect of difficulty and scrambling is probably an effect of the deviating hard emotion recognition category we have observed under figure 4.6, with an inverted balance due to our model’s choice of a base intercept.

We would like to point out that the null residual variance of our model indicates that it could be overparameterized. We have tried a series of alternate models (“scrambled” and “difficulty” - not including interaction -, “scrambled” alone, and “difficulty” alone), but all resulted in null residual variance - see tables 7.5, 7.6, and 7.7.

The reaction time model (table 4.7) paints a similar picture: with a significant value for the difficulty factor and no significance either for scrambling nor for scrambling and difficulty interaction. We would conclude that in spite of our reduced sample sizes and aforementioned reproducibility issues our scrambling algorithm represents a viable type of baseline.

It should be noted that though not significantly different, both of these simple visual recogni-

Model 1	
(Intercept)	0.02 [−0.02; 0.05]
difficulty:hard	0.07 [0.03; 0.11]*
scrambled:yes	0.00 [−0.04; 0.05]
difficulty:hard:scrambled:yes	−0.07 [−0.13; −0.01]*
Num. obs.	28
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.00
Variance: Residual	0.00

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 4.6: Mixed model fitted to the raw error rate data depicted in figure 4.6. Our factors are scrambling (yes or no) and difficulty (easy or hard). The model chooses "easy" and "not scrambled" as the intercept value. Difficulty and scrambling show no significant factor value, while their interaction does. The base intercept is not significant meaning that the base error rate of the model may not be reliably considered to lie above zero.

Model 1	
(Intercept)	1.56 [1.32; 1.79]*
difficulty:hard	0.30 [0.21; 0.39]*
scrambled:yes	0.01 [−0.09; 0.10]
difficulty:hard:scrambled:yes	−0.06 [−0.19; 0.07]
Num. obs.	896
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.07
Variance: Residual	0.25

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 4.7: Mixed model fitted to the raw reaction time data depicted in figure 4.5. Our factors are scrambling (yes or no) and difficulty (easy or hard). The model chooses "easy" and "not scrambled" as the intercept value. The base intercept is significant, indicating reaction times of the model are above zero. The difficulty factor is also positive and significant meaning that difficulty adds to response latency. All other factors are not significantly other than zero.

tion reaction times undershoot their counterpart emotion recognition reaction times. In light of this we have decided to use a 6 px kernel- and 10 px cluster-scrambled image baseline for difficult emotion recognition, and a 6 px kernel- and 22 px cluster-scrambled image baseline for easy emotion recognition.

4.5.2 Reaction Times

Figure 4.2 confirms our assumption that reaction times for the difficult emotion recognition condition are significantly different from (one-tailed related sample t-test p -value of 2.6×10^{-12}), and higher than for the easy condition. The overall results also support our assumption that there is a downward trend in reaction times over increasing scrambling cluster sizes. Additionally, mainly in trials with simple cluster-based scrambling (section 4.4.1 we see the emergence of a plateau-phase over higher scrambling cluster sizes.

This plateau suggests that scrambling cluster sizes of 14 px, 18 px, 22 px, and 26 px seen in figure 4.2 possessed the same recognition-relevant quality, which the 6 px scrambling cluster - at least - did not. If this purported feature is to explain the reaction time distribution, it should emerge at a scrambling cluster size of around 10 px. Visual scrutiny of the images suggested that the emergent feature may be recognizable facial elements - more precisely the eyes (with the iris having an outer diameter of approximately 8 px).

To test our hypothesis and define a more appropriate baseline for simple visual recognition, we devised a new set of experiments - described in section 4.3.3.2, and analyzed in section 4.4.2. An obvious feature there was the disappearance of the plateau phase, which supports our hypothesis regarding its emergence due to facial features with a horizontal and/or vertical spatial frequency of around 8 px. This is - however - only partly corroborated by other composite scrambling test runs, as seen in supplementary figures 7.4 and 7.5.

In section 4.3.2.2 we have detailed our decision to settle for a 4 s reaction time window, the predicted ideal cropping being 4.51 s, as calculated in section 4.4.1. In figure 4.7 we see that reaction times seem to fade approximately 0.5 s before our cut-off, and the fitted normal distribution does not indicate expected results beyond that point. We take these results as confirmation that our selected cut-off time is not over-stringent for the selected conditions (easy and hard emotion recognition, plus visual recognition of scrambled images processed with a 6 px scrambling kernel and 11 px and 23 px scrambling cluster respectively).

4.5.3 Error Rates

Our error rate distribution over categories proves difficult to interpret. It is obvious for one thing that error rates for most categories vary greatly among participants. A significant effect indicating that regardless of reaction times, difficult emotion recognition prompts a higher rate than all other conditions is documented under section 4.4.2.

4.5.4 Data Reliability

As our sample sizes are reduced, we acknowledge the limited reliability with which we can make claims pertaining to the general population.

We would, however, also like to indicate that both inter-trial and inter-participant variability is high (as seen in figure 4.5). The accuracy of the determined mean (reflected by the standard errors of figure 4.5) could be improved by more extensive testing - though the usefulness of doing so with respect to our search for an optimal baseline would be limited. Regardless of the quality of our mean, reaction times on individual trials would still often coincide even for less stringent or sub-optimal choices of a baseline. This would happen on the trial level, as well as on the *participant mean* level. Please see the standard deviations in figure 4.5 for a graphical representation of where approximately 68% of data points reside for each condition.

Chapter 5

Results

5.1 Participant Response Analysis

We are testing parameters of the participant input in our main experiments similarly to how we have assessed our preliminary trials (in section 4.4). The purpose of this analysis is to determine the extent to which we can rely on our baseline in the further investigation of this data set.

Due to equipment malfunction participant input data is only available for 8 of our 12 participants.

5.1.1 Reaction Times

The reaction times for our experiment are shown in figure 5.1. An obvious feature (especially in comparison to the reaction time relationships we sought to find in section 4.4) is the highly significant difference between easy emotion recognition and “easy” pattern recognition - two tailed paired t-test p -value of 8.8×10^{-4} .

To further describe this potentially disruptive development for our baseline, we have fitted a mixed model with reaction time as our dependent variable, emotion and difficulty as our factors (independent variables), and ID (participant) as our random variable. The model listed in table 5.1 gives a quantitative description confirming that pattern recognition trials prompted significantly higher reaction times. The emergence of a significant interaction factor in the model indicates that among the easy and hard pattern recognition trials, the difference in reaction times does not correspond directly to what the effect of the difficulty factor prescribes.

Figure 5.1: Reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Reaction times for non-response trials were not counted. The error bars represent the standard deviation.

	Model 1
(Intercept)	1.97 [1.70; 2.24]*
difficulty:hard	0.50 [0.41; 0.59]*
scrambled:yes	0.36 [0.27; 0.44]*
difficulty:hard:scrambled:yes	-0.43 [-0.55; -0.30]*
Num. obs.	986
Num. groups: ID	8
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.11
Variance: Residual	0.25

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 5.1: Mixed model fitted to the raw reaction times depicted in figure 5.1. Our factors are scrambling (yes or no) and difficulty (easy or hard). The model chooses "easy" and "not scrambled" as the intercept value. Difficulty shows a significant positive effect, which is to be expected. Scrambling also shows a significant positive effect - meaning that pattern recognition trials have higher reaction times. This reaction time difference is also not a global offset as difficulty and scrambling interact to form a significant negative effect.

5.1.2 Error Rates

Additionally, we have performed an error rate analysis to check for baseline weaknesses (as previously found in section 4.4.2).

Figure 5.2: Error rates for Hariri-style face matching. The error bars represent the standard deviation. Bar-plots with zero-height have been slightly indented for better visibility.

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	7	0.13	0.02		
difficulty	1	0.14	0.14	14.59	0.0005
scrambled	1	0.04	0.04	4.06	0.0513
difficulty:scrambled	1	0.07	0.07	7.86	0.0080
Residuals	37	0.35	0.01		

Table 5.2: Two-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 5.2. The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability obtained results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

Both figure 5.2 and the ANOVA test run on the portrayed data (under table 5.2) show that the baseline is not robust in terms of error rates. Note that the highly significant effect of the difficulty factor is not a weakness in the model per se - changes in error rates over difficulty alone would be acceptable and expected. The significant interaction effect of difficulty and scrambling, however, indicates that the given difficulty effect on emotion recognition trials is not reproduced by pattern recognition trials, thus coming to the detriment of the pattern recognition baseline.

5.2 Pupillometry - Methodological Reliability

Seeing as we are performing the debut pupillometric study on our present set-up, we have decided to perform at least a rough quality assessment for our measurements. A number of possible inaccuracies became apparent during data acquisition (described in detail under section 3.4.2) - and we are addressing these accordingly in the following paragraphs.

To reiterate, Y-axis pupil diameter is often obfuscated by eyelid coverage. Seeing as X-axis diameter incurs no such interference, we believe a simple analysis of correlation can show in how far our measurements are congruent and in how far Y-axis measurements are reliable.

Figure 5.3: Correlation between X-axis and Y-axis pupil diameters on measurement data points. Raw data points are shown in faint gray, and per-participant per-timepoint (relative to trial onset) means are shown in green. The regression line is drawn in magenta. To decrease cluttering, only one in three raw data points is plotted.

Figure 5.3 shows raw data points and means for pupil diameters. Due to the overwhelming amount of raw data points sharing the same variance, Pearson's r is numerically undefined for our raw data. We are thus fitting the correlation to the data point means. Here we see a Pearson's r of 9.7×10^{-1} and a p -value for non-correlation best approximated within the 64 bit numerical range as 0. It is safe to conclude from this result that our measurements are congruent. We will thus be using the mean of X-axis and Y-axis diameters as our preferred diameter approximation.

The observations we made during data acquisition pertaining to interference from the eyelids

with Y-axis measurements are however also confirmed to be true. A slight offshoot of raw data points is visible for higher values underneath the regression curve. This very probably represents single measurements during which the eyelid partially covered the pupil. While this offshoot is obscured for mean values, its effect can be traced in the linear formula of the regression line (the computed least-squares solution to a linear matrix equation $Y = aX + b$): $y = 1.1x - 8.4$. The y -intercept (-8.4) indicates that there is a fixed offset between X-axis and Y-axis measurements, by which Y-axis values are smaller than X-axis values across our measurement range (approx [20; 75]).

5.3 Per-Condition Pupil Dilation Response

In this section we are presenting how our conditions of interest (CoI) affect the pupil dilation response.

5.3.1 Time-Agnostic Comparison

We first examine the overall pupil dilation prompted by our conditions of interest. A bar plot showing participant dilation values and population values of per-participant means is presented under figure 5.4. All values in this figure are normalized to the *global* mean of inter-trial (fixation) dilation size, and thus also reflect inter-participant variability. We notice a strong overall coherence of per-condition pupil dilation values on the participant level, but high variability of pupil dilation between participants.

There appears to be a main effect of condition of interest for the mean pupil dilation, as seen in the ANOVA summary of table 5.3. Visual scrutiny of the bar plot, as well as post-hoc t-tests indicate that inter-trial pupil dilation is significantly different from all other conditions - with related measurements t-test p -values of 3.3×10^{-2} , 3.3×10^{-2} , 4.7×10^{-2} , and 4.9×10^{-2} (for the comparison of inter-trial means with easy emotion matching, hard emotion matching, easy pattern matching, and hard pattern matching trials respectively).

Based on the high inter-participant variability noticed in this analysis, we are conducting time-course plotting and data analysis by normalizing all measurements to the *per-participant* intertrial mean value.

Figure 5.4: Bar plots of pupil dilation integrated over the entire time course. The Y-axis values are proportional to the global fixation (inter-trial interval) pupil size. The error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

Figure 5.5: Pupil dilation over time. The values are proportional to the mean pupil dilation size during fixation (the inter-trial interval). Shaded areas represent the standard errors of the mean. The vertical line represents the mean reaction time. Plotted data was down-sampled to 15 Hz.

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	11	12.47	1.13		
CoI	4	0.32	0.08	4.90	0.0023
Residuals1	44	0.72	0.02		

Table 5.3: One-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 5.4. Here we test the effect of our conditions of interest ("CoI") on mean pupil dilation. The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability of present results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

5.3.2 Task Engagement: Trial vs. Inter-Trial

Figure 5.5 shows the general time course for all trial conditions and for inter-trial (fixation) periods. The data indicates that trial conditions prompt a rapid increase in pupil diameter (over the first 0.5 s) followed by a more attenuated slope, which is terminated by a steady decline starting about 0.5 s before the mean reaction time.

The time course during fixation sees an initial high amplitude decrease of pupil area, followed by a slow recovery phase. In this per-participant normalized analysis, means integrating all values across the time course (per-participant) are significantly higher for trial sessions than for inter-trial intervals - with a related sample t-test p -value of 1.4×10^{-2} .

5.3.3 Difficulty: Easy vs. Difficult Trials

The pupil dilation response time courses of easy and difficult matching trials - integrating both recognition types (emotional and scrambled faces) - are plotted in figure 5.6. This graphic shows that upon stimulus presentation pupil area experiences a short dip, followed by an apparent rapid increase for easy and hard emotion recognition respectively. After a seemingly steady phase of around 1.5 s pupil area experiences a slow decrease over the rest of the trial duration.

A few differences in easy vs. difficult task time course are also apparent. One of the most accessible to basic statistical models is the main effect of condition over the latter half of the trial time window (2 s to 4 s). The summary of a mixed model fitted to this linear decay phase can be seen in table 5.4.

Further features relating to an interaction factor for time and condition are less accessible to statistical modelling due to the complex non-linear shape of the pupil dilation time courses. Such trends include: a starting dip in pupil dilation (which seems more pronounced for hard

Figure 5.6: Pupil dilation over time for easy and difficult matching. The values are proportional to the mean pupil dilation size during fixation (here 1.0). Shaded areas represent the standard errors of the mean. Vertical lines represent mean reaction times. Plotted data was down-sampled to 15 Hz.

Model 1	
(Intercept)	1.17 (0.00)***
CoI:hard	0.03 (0.01)***
Num. obs.	4344

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Table 5.4: Mixed model fitted to the latter half of the time course depicted in figure 5.6. The independent variable is CoI (condition of interest) which is either "hard" or "difficult". Time and ID (participant) are defined as random variables. Confidence intervals are shown in the parentheses.

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	11	8.42	0.77		
CoI	1	0.03	0.03	2.96	0.0874
dTime	7	0.28	0.04	4.09	0.0004
CoI:dTime	7	0.07	0.01	1.03	0.4095
Residuals1	165	1.60	0.01		

Table 5.5: Two-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 5.6. Here we test the effect of our conditions of interest ("CoI") and of discrete time octiles ("dTime"). The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability of obtained results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

emotion matching) and a relationship between mean reaction times and pupil dilation decay onset. A popular analysis method in psychology - dividing the time into discrete bins and performing an ANOVA with a simple linear model (thereby circumventing issues arising from non-linearity and autocorrelation) - also fails to find significance for anything but the time factor (as seen in table 5.5).

5.3.4 Emotionality: Emotional vs. Scrambled Trials

Figure 5.7: Pupil dilation over time for matching of either emotional or scrambled faces. The values are proportional to the mean pupil dilation size during fixation (here 1.0). Shaded areas represent the standard errors of the mean. Vertical lines represent mean reaction times. Plotted data was down-sampled to 15 Hz.

In the comparison of emotion and pattern matching we find a picture very similar to the

Model 1	
(Intercept)	1.16 (0.01) ^{***}
CoI:scrambled	0.04 (0.01) ^{***}
Num. obs.	4344

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Table 5.6: Mixed model fitted to the latter half of the time course depicted in figure 5.7. The independent variable is CoI (condition of interest) which is either "hard" or "difficult". Time and ID (participant) are defined as random variables.

one described in section 5.3.3. In figure 5.7, first we see a rapid increase in pupil area for both of these conditions. Following this initial trend the pupil area appears to plateau over approximately 1.0 s before trending upwards again and subsequently downwards.

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	11	8.92	0.81		
CoI	1	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.5591
dTime	7	0.34	0.05	3.76	0.0008
CoI:dTime	7	0.11	0.02	1.26	0.2751
Residuals1	165	2.10	0.01		

Table 5.7: Two-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 5.7. Here we test the effect of our conditions of interest ("CoI") and of discrete time octiles ("dTime"). The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability of obtained results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

There is a pronounced and significant main effect of condition (emotion vs. pattern recognition) over the latter half of the time course - from 2 s to 4 s. A model of this effect is documented in the mixed model summary from table 5.6. Additional scrutiny of the time course (as approximated by distinct time octiles) also fails to find significant interactions - as seen in table 5.7.

5.3.5 Emotion: Happy vs. Fearful Emotion Trials

In comparing happy and fearful emotion recognition tasks we find an overall similar time course picture. Pupil area experiences a rapid increase, and this initial trend, the pupil area appears to plateau for approximately 1.5 s before trending downwards for the remainder of the trial time.

For this particular comparison there seems to be a main effect of condition (happy vs. fearful

Figure 5.8: Pupil dilation over time for emotional faces matching. The values are proportional to the mean pupil dilation size during fixation (here 1.0). Shaded areas represent the standard errors of the mean. Vertical lines represent mean reaction times. Plotted data was down-sampled to 15 Hz.

emotion recognition), which is independent of time. This is also indicated by an ANOVA performed on discrete time octiles (intervals of 0.5 ms each) - the summary of which is presented in table 5.8. Overall the pupil dilation is considerably stronger for fearful emotion recognition than for happy emotion recognition, until approximately the last octile (3.5 s to 4.0 s), where the main effect of the “happy” condition is counteracted by the “happy”-dTime interaction (explicit linear model shown under supplementary materials, in table 7.1).

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	11	6.21	0.56		
CoI	1	0.11	0.11	10.48	0.0015
dTime	7	0.28	0.04	3.96	0.0005
CoI:dTime	7	0.02	0.00	0.31	0.9478
Residuals1	165	1.70	0.01		

Table 5.8: Two-way repeated measure ANOVA table for the data depicted in figure 5.8. Here we test the effect of our conditions of interest (“CoI”) and of discrete time octiles (“dTime”). The $Pr(> F)$ value indicates the adjusted probability of obtained results occurring by chance if the means of our defined categories are equal.

5.4 Condition-Dependent Brain Activity Contrasts

The following brain activation analyses have been thresholded at an uncorrected p -value of 0.001 and a spatial extent threshold of 20 voxels. None of the subsequently presented contrast pairs presented any activity in the LC ROI at an uncorrected p -value threshold of 0.001 and a spatial extent threshold of 0 voxels.

5.4.1 Difficult vs. Easy Pattern Matching

No significant brain activation was obtained for the contrast of difficult pattern matching trials against the baseline of easy pattern matching tasks at our preferred threshold. The analysis of the inverse contrast has similarly yielded no activation clusters.

5.4.2 Emotion vs. Pattern Recognition

We have analysed emotion vs. pattern recognition contrasts separately for the two matched pairs: 100 % emotion and 22 px scrambling; and 40 % emotion and 10 px scrambling respectively. This was done in lieu of binning the two sets of conditions together chiefly because the two contrasts are not comparable in terms of difficulty difference between conditions (as shown in section 5.1). For the subsequently presented data we define pattern recognition as the baseline, and describe activation prompted by emotion recognition as relative to that baseline.

5.4.2.1 100 % Emotion vs. 22 px Scrambling

A number of regions show activity in this contrast at our preferred uncorrected significance ($p = 0.001$) and spatial extent (20 voxel) thresholds. These clusters are detailed in table 5.9.

The activation clusters with the highest degree of significance are thus located within the right medial temporal gyrus (cluster A), the right hemisphere of the cerebellum (cluster B), the right superior parietal lobule (cluster C), and the right superior occipital gyrus (cluster D). Lower peak voxel significance (FWE-corrected p -value of 0.746, cluster H) has been found for amygdala/hippocampus activation, which we present for illustrative purposes alongside the precuneus activation of cluster C in figure 5.9. Other areas presenting activation clusters are the right and left lateral occipitotemporal gyri (cluster E and G respectively), the left cerebellum (cluster F), and the left superior temporal gyrus (cluster I).

	Cluster[px]	Peak-Level					
		$P_{\text{FWE-corr}}$	$P_{\text{FDR-corr}}$	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]
A	147	0.041	0.39	9.31	54	-73	1
		0.302	0.428	7.57	60	-58	7
		0.961	0.545	5.68	51	-43	7
B	57	0.051	0.39	9.11	33	-82	-35
		0.919	0.541	5.95	42	-76	-35
C	155	0.278	0.428	7.63	3	-52	43
		0.768	0.428	6.52	9	-61	34
		0.918	0.541	5.95	-9	-46	37
D	31	0.449	0.428	7.25	18	-88	-32
		1.0	0.721	4.73	12	-82	-29
E	36	0.636	0.428	6.93	39	-52	-14
		0.984	0.623	5.43	39	-46	-23
		0.998	0.642	5.05	42	-34	-11
F	26	0.73	0.428	6.64	-30	-85	-32
G	24	0.744	0.428	6.6	-39	-52	-17
H	36	0.746	0.428	6.59	-21	-10	-20
I	20	0.785	0.428	6.47	-45	14	-23

Table 5.9: Summary statistics for brain activation clusters in the contrast of easy emotion matching trials against a baseline of easy pattern matching trials. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

Figure 5.9: Graphical depiction of brain activation in the contrast of easy emotion matching trials against a baseline of easy pattern matching trials; with cross-hairs positioned at the corresponding highest significance voxel of the cluster (as listed under table 5.9).

The inverse of this condition yielded activation clusters in the occipital and superior parietal lobules with higher significance in the left cerebral hemisphere. These clusters are accurately documented in table 5.10. They are distributed across the left angular gyrus (cluster A) and lingual gyrus (cluster B), the right superior parietal lobule (cluster C) and lateral occipitotem-

poral gyrus (cluster D), and the left lateral occipitotemporal gyrus (cluster E).

		Peak-Level					
Cluster[px]		$P_{\text{FWE-corr}}$	$P_{\text{FDR-corr}}$	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]
A	256	0.022	0.129	9.9	-27	-70	31
		0.692	0.323	6.76	-24	-88	16
		0.811	0.323	6.38	-33	-85	19
B	74	0.031	0.129	9.58	-9	-91	-5
		0.396	0.323	7.35	0	-88	-2
		1.0	0.634	4.72	-18	-85	-8
C	187	0.65	0.323	6.89	18	-64	61
		0.802	0.323	6.41	39	-79	10
		0.895	0.323	6.06	36	-88	7
D	23	0.894	0.323	6.06	27	-40	-11
		0.993	0.463	5.26	27	-34	-17
E	38	0.967	0.37	5.63	-30	-46	-11
		0.975	0.37	5.63	-30	-46	-11
		0.975	0.384	5.55	-27	-61	-11
		1.0	0.928	4.15	-30	-73	-5

Table 5.10: Summary statistics for brain activation clusters in the contrast of easy pattern matching trials against a baseline of easy emotion matching trials. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

5.4.2.2 40 % Emotion vs. 10 px Scrambling

Brain activation evoked by difficult emotion matching trials relative to difficult pattern matching trials was distributed over the clusters listed in table 5.11. These clusters are confined to the right occipitoparietal and occipitotemporal lobules (with the exception of cluster H, which is located in the right frontal lobe; and cluster B in the left lateral occipitotemporal gyrus).

Of these clusters we would like to illustrate the recurring activation cluster in the right pre-cuneus (E), and the most significant activation clusters (A and B) in the right and left lateral occipitotemporal gyri - see figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10: Graphical depiction of brain activation in the contrast of difficult emotion matching trials against a baseline of difficult pattern matching trials; with cross-hairs positioned at the corresponding highest significance voxel of the cluster (as listed under table 5.11).

Cluster[px]	Peak-Level						
	$P_{FWE-corr}$	$P_{FDR-corr}$	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]	
A	45	0.154	0.407	8.13	39	-49	-17
B	20	0.795	0.407	6.47	-39	-52	-17
C	30	0.838	0.407	6.32	42	-79	-11
		0.937	0.434	5.88	45	-73	-5
D	35	0.86	0.407	6.24	54	-64	4
		0.992	0.5	5.31	48	-55	7
		1.0	0.742	4.52	48	-64	19
E	28	0.864	0.407	6.23	3	-64	28
F	29	0.985	0.496	5.46	36	17	22

Table 5.11: Summary statistics for brain activation clusters in the contrast of difficult emotion matching trials against a baseline of difficult pattern matching trials. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

The inverse contrast of this condition - difficult pattern recognition compared to a baseline of difficult emotion recognition yields activation clusters in high agreement with those of the inverse contrast from section 5.4.2.1. These activation clusters are accurately documented by table 5.12. They span across the left angular gyrus (cluster A), superior parietal lobule (cluster B), and putamen (cluster C), the right superior parietal lobule (cluster D), insula (cluster E), and superior parietal lobule (cluster F), the left medial occipitotemporal gyrus (cluster G), and the right cerebellum (cluster H).

Cluster[px]	Peak-Level						
	P _{FWE-corr}	P _{FDR-corr}	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]	
A	93	0.006	0.184	11.27	-42	-43	46
		0.877	0.491	6.17	-48	-49	34
B	355	0.235	0.465	7.77	-18	-67	52
		0.449	0.465	7.25	-36	-82	16
		0.607	0.465	7.02	-36	-79	28
C	32	0.645	0.465	6.94	-24	11	-11
		0.657	0.465	6.9	-24	17	-2
D	402	0.684	0.465	6.82	15	-67	61
		0.695	0.465	6.79	27	-64	49
		0.717	0.465	6.72	36	-82	7
E	20	0.828	0.492	6.36	30	23	-2
		0.98	0.492	5.53	36	20	-11
F	21	0.858	0.492	6.25	39	-46	58
G	35	0.961	0.492	5.72	-27	-58	-8
		0.997	0.566	5.15	-27	-46	-17
H	28	0.991	0.545	5.34	15	-67	-38
		0.994	0.552	5.25	18	-52	-41
		0.998	0.588	5.05	9	-58	-47

Table 5.12: Summary statistics for brain activation clusters in the contrast of difficult pattern matching trials against a baseline of difficult emotion matching trials. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

5.4.3 Strong vs. Weak emotion Intensity

As described in detail under section 3.3.1, “easy” and “difficult” emotion matching are designed based on face images with more obvious (more concentrated - 100%) or less obvious (less concentrated - 40%) emotions. Comparing the emotion matching trials based on difficulty (difficult emotion matching against a baseline of easy emotion matching) shows no significant brain activation at our preferred significance and spatial extent threshold. The cluster closest to significance is detailed in table 5.13, and was identified at an uncorrected p -value of 0.005 and a spatial extent threshold of 20 voxels.

Cluster[px]	Peak-Level						
	P _{FWE-corr}	P _{FDR-corr}	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]	
A	26	1.0	0.981	4.06	45	20	25
		1.0	0.981	3.17	42	5	28

Table 5.13: Summary statistics for brain activation clusters in the contrast of difficult emotion matching tasks against easy emotion matching tasks. The single cluster activated in this contrast lies in the right middle frontal gyrus. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

The inverse contrast of the aforementioned comparison - easy emotion recognition against

a baseline of difficult emotion recognition - is also the contrast of strong emotional stimuli against a baseline of weak emotional stimuli. This comparison yields many more activation clusters (at our preferred thresholds) - all of which are detailed under table 5.14. The area covered by these clusters is ample and includes the left superior temporal gyrus (cluster A), the left medial frontal gyrus (cluster D), and the posterior cingulate cortex (“PCC”, cluster B). We present an illustrative example of the latter two of these clusters under figure 5.11.

Other areas over which the clusters of this contrast spread include the left angular gyrus (cluster C), the right superior occipital lobe (cluster E) and middle temporal gyrus (cluster F), the left superior frontal lobe (cluster G), the left frontal lobe (cluster H) and superior frontal gyrus (cluster I).

Figure 5.11: Graphical depiction of brain activation in the contrast of strong emotion stimulus trials against a baseline of weak emotion stimulus trials; with cross-hairs positioned at the corresponding highest significance voxel of the cluster (as listed under table 5.14).

5.5 Pupil Dilation Regression

In the subsequent analyses we threshold brain activation clusters at an uncorrected p -value of 0.001 and a spatial extent threshold of 0 voxels. The decrease in the spatial extent threshold from the 20 voxels of the previous section owes to our present use of a region of interest covering only a few dozen voxels.

For a first analysis attempt, the per-participant pupil area time course was downsampled to the TR (as detailed under section 3.5.2) - in order to be used as a regressor. This regressor (**Regressor I.**) was introduced as a condition in the first level analysis of the fMRI data (inde-

		Peak-Level					
	Cluster[px]	$P_{FWE-corr}$	$P_{FDR-corr}$	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]
A	137	0.002	0.074	12.9	-60	-16	-8
		0.332	0.303	7.49	-63	-25	-5
		0.343	0.303	7.47	-57	-34	-2
B	233	0.008	0.081	11.0	-3	-37	43
		0.157	0.303	8.11	-6	-31	37
		0.555	0.314	7.09	-12	-46	34
C	203	0.008	0.081	10.96	-42	-58	40
		0.476	0.303	7.21	-42	-58	31
		0.665	0.34	6.88	-48	-52	25
D	468	0.232	0.303	7.78	-6	56	13
		0.324	0.303	7.51	-6	50	-5
		0.432	0.303	7.28	0	59	4
E	85	0.24	0.303	7.76	21	-91	19
		0.88	0.354	6.16	6	-85	37
		0.975	0.458	5.58	18	-85	37
F	41	0.673	0.34	6.85	60	-19	-8
		0.977	0.458	5.55	60	-25	-14
		1.0	0.869	4.31	60	-7	-8
G	21	0.824	0.348	6.37	-12	38	46
		1.0	0.825	4.54	-15	35	34
H	21	0.911	0.38	6.02	21	-40	40
I	29	0.93	0.394	5.92	-24	32	46
		0.956	0.427	5.75	-33	20	49
		1.0	0.918	4.19	-30	29	40

Table 5.14: Summary statistics for brain activation clusters in the contrast of strong emotion stimulus trials against a baseline of weak emotion stimulus trials. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

pendent of the afore detailed conditions of interest). Subsequently the resulting per-participant contrasts were integrated to form population contrast in the second-level analysis.

This first regressor is not folded (not convoluted with the HRF), and turns out to be weakly correlated with a peak inside the Locus Coeruleus (LC) region of interest (ROI). This correlated voxel is located at the transition from the right LC nucleus to the fourth ventricle area and is documented in table 5.15, and shown in figure 5.12a.

	Cluster[px]	Peak-Level					
		P _{FWE-corr}	P _{FDR-corr}	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]
A	1	0.053	0.905	4.1	3	-37	-20

Table 5.15: Summary statistics for the LC ROI brain activation peak correlated with a raw pupil area time course regressor. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

For further clarification of results, three other regressors have been used to explore pupil dilation correlated activity in the fMRI data. These are:

- **Regressor II.** - A raw pupil area time series downsampled at 0.5 Hz (identical with regressor I.) convoluted with the HRF.
- **Regressor III.** - A pupil area time series differential (computed at on the pupil area data at the original 60 Hz) and subsequently downsampled at 0.5 Hz.
- **Regressor IV.** - A pupil area time series differential (computed at on the pupil area data at the original 60 Hz) and subsequently downsampled at 0.5 Hz and convoluted with the HRF.

Of these other regressors, the first two (II. and III.) did not identify any LC ROI activation. Regressor IV. - the HRF-convoluted pupil area time series differential - was correlated with LC ROI activation similar to the one identified by the raw pupil area time course regressor. The activation cluster is broader than the previously identified one, with a more significant peak voxel - but similarly lateralized towards the right LC nucleus. The brain activation data for this regressor is summarized under table 5.16 and depicted in figure 5.12b.

	Cluster[px]	Peak-Level					
		P _{FWE-corr}	P _{FDR-corr}	T	X[mm]	Y[mm]	Z[mm]
A	5	0.003	0.189	6.04	6	-34	-26
B	1	0.54	0.838	4.17	-6	-34	-26

Table 5.16: Summary statistics for the LC ROI brain activation peak correlated with a pupil area time course differential regressor convoluted with the HRF. FWE = Family-Wise Error; FDR = False Discovery Rate; X, Y, and Z coordinates given in MNI space.

(a) Unconvoluted regressor of raw pupil area time course.

(b) HRF-convoluted regressor of time course differential.

Figure 5.12: Graphical depiction of brain activation within the LC ROI correlated with 2 different pupil area regressors.

Chapter 6

Discussion

Here we present conclusions pertaining to our research focus topics (listed under section 2.5) which we draw based upon our behavioural, neuroimaging, and pupillometric experimental results.

6.1 Pyxrand's Stimuli for Non-Semantic Matching

A number of publications describe the use of scrambled face stimuli for their experiments - as baseline conditions or in other contexts [Lewis and Edmonds, 2005; Rakover and Cahlon, 2013]. The stimuli are often prepared either manually, or through time-consuming per-picture editing in an image manipulation program. Pyxrand [Christian, 2013e] simplifies this procedure by automatically scrambling images without any constraint on dimensions or ratio, and provides great customisability of its scrambling procedure. Though automated scrambling software already exists [Conway et al., 2008], its scope is a lot narrower and its algorithms are not released publicly.

The results presented under sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2 show that Pyxrand can produce stimulus images the matching of which can be tuned to the same time range as the matching of emotional face stimulus images. The emergence of a plateau phase in reaction times when using only cluster-based scrambling (see section 3.3.2 for technical descriptions), and its preponderant disappearance when using both kernel and cluster based scrambling, indicates that the software can provide both low-pass and high-pass filtering for facial features. This makes it suitable not only for rendering stimulus images non-semantic, but also for selectively excluding features used for semantic identification via their spatial frequencies. Data described under section 4.4.2 also shows that the various scrambling parameters offered by Pyxrand can be

successfully tweaked to vary reaction times (but apparently not error rates - see sections 5.1.2 and 4.4.2).

The non-replicability of our chosen pattern recognition baseline (seen under section 5.1.1) could be due to different performance attributes of either the different population or the different setting (inside the fMRI scanner). Elucidating this issue would require testing of multiple scrambling steps in the fMRI scanner, or in an environment closely resembling it.

Pyxrand also appears to have fulfilled the task of generating equiluminous baseline trial images, as we were unable to detect a rapid-onset effect of matching task type (emotional vs. pattern matching) in the comparison of pupil area documented under section 5.3.4 - as would be expected if the scrambled stimuli would trigger the pupillary light reflex. We believe that pixel interpolation effects which emerge upon image scaling could disrupt the stimulus equiluminance of processed and unprocessed images, though this would require a quantitative study of pixel gray values over different input image types.

We would like to conclude the assessment of Pyxrand by stating that its usability in experimental psychological contexts is tentatively validated, and that its transparent publication and versatile functionality would make it a valuable tool for visual cognition researchers dealing with topics even very remote from our own.

6.2 Pupillometric Time Course

6.2.1 Method Viability

Based on the X/Y-axis correlation data under section 5.2, and the visual coherence of time plots under section 5.3, we believe pupillometry is a viable method for use in our current fMRI set-up.

Mean pupil dilation levels, when normalized to the same baseline (as seen in section 5.3.1), show highly consistent per-participant trends but a strong inter-participant variability (the dynamic range of participant means being approximately 10 dB). We take the first of these observations as further support of the method's viability. The second observation, however, is difficult to explain simply by anatomical variability of pupil sizes and the task-independent variability of baseline pupil dilation. We posit that this high variability is due to variant distances from the eye to the camera, and different zoom levels of our optometric equipment in between trials.

As the pupil-to-camera distance is contingent on many factors including head size, we do not presume to accomplish measurements comparable in absolute terms between testing sessions. This comes somewhat to the detriment of pupillometry in our set-up, as we can thus only analyse changes in pupil size, and not baseline pupil diameters (which could be connected with participant genotype, emotional state progress over multiple sessions, or disease progress over multiple sessions).

6.2.2 Task Difficulty

Time courses of pupil dilation for easy and difficult trials (as seen in figure 5.6) follow a similar pattern over the first half of the trial duration, but present divergent trends for the latter half. As stimulus images remain on-screen regardless of participant input, we can tentatively exclude the possibility that this effect is due to changing visual input. We cannot fully do so due to the fact that visual input depends on gaze point, and we have not yet established a control for this - such an explanation is however highly improbable, as our stimulus pictures have a mean luminosity close to the background luminosity value.

We assume that this difference arises indeed from no other source than task difficulty. In pupillometry literature increased pupil dilation proportional with cognitive load and/or task difficulty is a solidly documented phenomenon [Piquado et al., 2010]. Our time course analysis seems, however, to the best of our knowledge unprecedented - whereby we would provide the first analysis of pupil dilation response parameters in a Hariri-style matching task. In describing the effects we documented, we would tentatively argue that the decrease in pupil dilation seen in easy trials (as opposed to hard trials) starts approximately 0.25s after the mean reaction time and is representative of task disengagement and reduced attention. Recent literature presents an opposite (pupil dilation, as opposed to constriction) effect of task disengagement [Franklin et al., 2013] - the authors, however, define the phenomenon of disengagement by self-reported mind wandering. We do not assume our participants to engage in mind wandering during the pupil constriction period, and thus do not believe these findings to be conflicting.

Due to our reduced participant sample size ($n=12$), our evaluation of the time course data is only sparsely significant. We believe that more refined modelling of the time course data (using time as a continuous variable and analysing data at the original sampling frequency of 60 Hz), together with a slightly increased participant sample size would be sufficient for a highly accurate description of pupil dilation time courses with solid significance levels. For such an analysis we believe the usage of mixed models which can account for autocorrelation

(as for example the ones provided by R's `nlme:lme`) would be viable. We are however yet to find a formula adequate for fitting our data to.

6.2.3 Task Type Effect

In the comparison of emotion matching task pupil dilation and pattern matching task pupil dilation time courses, we see a very similar picture to that described in section 6.2.2. The very high similarity between the time courses plotted in figures 5.6 and 5.7 is probably due to the difference in difficulty which accompanies the task type.

This difference in difficulty was unintended, and we have sought to minimize the chance of its emergence via the preliminary testing detailed in section 4. The scrambling parameters which we have thus chosen under section 4.5.1 were shown to be unsatisfactory by the reaction time analysis performed under section 5.1.1. Summarizing this state of affairs, we would conclude that there is no reliable way to disentangle task type and difficulty based on our data.

Nonetheless it appears that we can exclude an effect of type task which is both strong and opposite to the effect of difficulty (meaning that we can fairly certainly exclude the possibility of emotion matching eliciting an increase in pupil diameter over the latter half of the time course). We make this educated guess based on the thought that in any other case the similarity between the two comparisons would be in some way reduced.

In the comparison of task vs. non-task pupil dilation (seen in section 5.3.2) we notice an initial increase of pupil area in trial periods and an initial decrease of pupil area in non-trial periods. This is indeed congruent with the fact that our fixation cross is lighter in colour than the mean grey value of our stimulus images. However, due to the small area of the cross and the gradual re-widening of the pupil over a time when only the cross is displayed, we propose that these phasic dilation and constriction effects are caused by task engagement and disengagement processes (rather than the pupillary light reflex).

6.2.4 Emotional Valence Effect

In the comparison of pupil dilation time courses for trials using happy or fearful target stimuli, we only notice a main effect of condition, whereby happy faces prompt an overall increase in pupil area. As opposed to the previous comparisons we do not suggest the presence of any time-condition interaction trend.

Our results from section 5.3.5 - when seen alongside the results of the other aforementioned comparisons - suggest that pupil dilation can also be affected *independently* of task-related

attention allocation. This dichotomy of task parameter effects on pupil dilation is to the best of our knowledge first documented in this study, and in agreement with both recent work on pupil dilation as a marker for cognitive load *and* with initial studies on pupil dilation as a marker for affect [Nunally et al., 1967; Bradshaw, 1967]. With the greatest caution we would also like to suggest that this may indicate a potential relationship of pupil dilation with both the NA and the 5-HT systems (the backdrop of which we have extensively discussed in section 2.2).

6.2.5 Per-Condition Brain Activation

As seen under section 5.4, our paradigm is inefficient in eliciting strong brain activation responses. Additionally, considerable signal detection power is lost due to pattern matching being roughly equal for both “easy” and “difficult” pattern matching.

In the comparison of easy and difficult pattern matching trials (see section 5.4.1) we see no activation in either the easy vs. hard or hard vs. easy contrasts. In liaison with the reaction time comparison of these conditions (performed under section 5.1.1) it becomes obvious that our pattern matching contrasts were indeed not significantly different in difficulty.

In the comparison of easy emotion matching tasks with easy pattern matching tasks, we see what we believe are repercussions of the same baseline flaws. Activation of the precuneus (which we see in this comparison and illustrate in figure 5.9a) is commonly associated with the default mode network, and is considered the main hub thereof [Cavanna, 2007]. The default mode network is well-documented as a contrast of *not* performing a task against the baseline of performing a task [Raichle and Snyder, 2007]. We believe the precuneus activation in our participants is indicative of the reduced difficulty of easy emotion matching compared to easy pattern matching (confirmed by the reaction time analysis under section 5.1.1). It is, however, possible that precuneus activation is in part prompted by stimulus emotionality, as this area has also been implicated in semantic emotional processing [Maddock et al., 2003]. We also see amygdala activation in the contrast of easy emotion matching against easy pattern matching (as illustrated under figure 5.9b). We attribute this to the emotional quality of the stimuli used for this condition and note that this is in congruence with documented amygdala reactivity to emotional stimuli [Hariri et al., 2002].

Amygdala activation is absent in the contrast of hard emotion matching vs. hard pattern matching (see section 5.4.2.2). We believe this indicates that the threshold emotionality value for amygdala activation is not superseded by the 40% emotional stimuli used for the hard emotion matching trials in our task. The precuneus also shows activity in this contrast,

which we find curious, seeing as according to the reaction time analysis under section 5.1.1, there should be no difference in difficulty between these trial types. Moreover, the error rate analysis (under section 5.1.2) suggests that the hard emotion matching condition may be *more* difficult than the hard pattern matching condition. We can not rule out the possibility of emotionality-related precuneus activation and the possibility of difference in task difficulty which is not accounted for by error rates or reaction times, though our data is insufficient to formulate a model of these phenomena.

In the comparison of hard emotion matching against easy emotion matching we do not see any significant activation clusters. As there is indeed a difficulty difference (as documented by reaction time *and* error rate analysis in sections 5.1.1 and 5.1.2) between these trials, we can only conclude that brain areas implicated in task-compliance would become obvious over a larger sample size. The inverse contrast, easy emotion matching vs. difficult emotion matching (which is incidentally also the contrast of strongly emotional stimulus images vs. faintly emotional stimulus images) surprisingly shows little activation in areas documented for their engagement in emotional processing. A surprising hallmark of this comparison is the absence of amygdala activation. Instead of activation best described in terms of emotion perception we see a cluster pattern highly consistent with the default mode network (see figure 5.4.3). We take this as a marker of reduced trial difficulty which is consistent with our comparison of easy emotion matching vs. easy pattern matching.

6.2.6 Pupil Area Correlated LC Activity

In section 5.5 we describe activity within the locus coeruleus (LC) region of interest (ROI). The pupil dilatory effect of LC activity is a common assumption made in literature - based on circumstantial evidence and animal studies (as extensively described under section 2.4). Until now, however, the relationship was never functionally imaged in humans. To the best of our knowledge our attempt is the first to succeed in documenting a correlation between pupil dilation and neuronal activity in the human LC, all while performing rigorous scrutiny of coordinates (by the use of a ROI based on *in vivo*, fMRI-localization of the LC).

The LC activity is - interestingly - not correlated with the HRF convoluted regressor computed from the time course of the pupil area. It is in fact better correlated (approaching significance) with the *not convoluted* regressor computed from the pupil area time course. This is surprising in as far as fMRI measures BOLD responses only (which are used only after an HRF deconvolution as a proxy for neuronal activity). Under the assumption that the activation seen under

figure 5.12a is not an artefact, this would suggest that the function of pupil area in terms of LC neuronal activity is somewhat similar to the HRF.

A slightly different model for the relationship between LC neuronal activity and pupil dilation emerges from the analysis of our fMRI data with an HRF-convoluted regressor obtained from the first differential of the pupil area time course. This regressor identifies a significant bilateral (and slightly lateralized) activation highly coincident with in vivo documented LC coordinates. It is interesting to note that while the left LC is slightly larger in cell count than the right [Mouton et al., 1994], our activity pattern was lateralized to the right. In light of the regressor-correlated activity illustrated under figure 5.12b we would propose that LC neuronal activity prompts pupil dilation (as an active phenomenon), but is not required for dilation level maintenance. This would mean that the LC acts only as a pupil dilation homeostasis regulator, and would also explain why its correlation with pupil dilation in humans has been so elusive. We would be cautious with overly detailed interpretation of this correlation's kinetics, as the BOLD response in the brainstem has been documented as non-canonical [Astafiev et al., 2010]. This is a crucial issue, since the accuracy with which we describe activation kinetics is inextricably contingent on the accuracy with which we approximate the brain stem BOLD.

6.2.7 Outlook

Our study has presented first experimental results attesting the methodological validity of the feature obfuscation script Pyxrand. We additionally demonstrate pupillometry as a viable neurophysiological research method for matching paradigms performed in the fMRI-oculometry set-up of the Central Institute of Mental Health. We believe both Pyxrand and pupillometry have a potential for application in a very broad range of neuroscience projects.

We tentatively describe pupil dilation time course kinetics in matching tasks, and confirm previous findings from pupillometric literature. Our research widens the spectrum of experimental paradigms for which established pupillometric models exist, though we acknowledge that the accuracy of our models would greatly benefit from a larger participant sample size.

The whole brain analysis results of this study are undermined by the codependence of task type (emotion vs. pattern matching) and task difficulty (easy vs. hard). Regardless of this noteworthy issue, we identify a number of significant brain activation clusters which are mostly in accord with peer-reviewed literature. We look towards a better pattern matching condition and a higher participant sample size to refine our results.

Our study provides ample evidence of a significant relationship between pupil dilation and LC activity. We look towards increased participant sample sizes, and analysis with various (experimental) BOLD models in order to even more accurately describe the phenomenon we have uncovered. In light of an accurate model for the relationship between pupil dilation and LC activity, usage of pupil dilation as a portable, rapid, low-cost proxy for LC activation (and possibly activity within other interconnected systems) would be within immediate reach.

Bibliography

- Brigit Abler and Henrik Kessler. Emotion regulation questionnaire – eine deutschsprachige fassung des erq von gross und john. *Diagnostica*, (55):144–152, 2009.
- Douglas G. Altman and J Martin Bland. Standard deviations and standard errors. *BMJ*, 331(7521):903, Oct 2005. doi: 10.1136/bmj.331.7521.903. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.331.7521.903>.
- Christa J. Anderson, John Colombo, and Kathryn E. Unruh. Pupil and salivary indicators of autonomic dysfunction in autism spectrum disorder. *Developmental Psychobiology*, 55(5):465–482, Jul 2013. doi: 10.1002/dev.21051. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/dev.21051>.
- David R. Anderson, Dennis J. Sweeney, and Thomas A. Williams. *Statistics for Business and Economics, 6th Edition*. West Group, 1996. ISBN 0314063781. URL <http://www.amazon.com/Statistics-Business-Economics-6th-Edition/dp/0314063781%3FSubscriptionId%3D0JYN1NVW651KCA56C102%26tag%3Dtechkie-20%26linkCode%3Dxm2%26camp%3D2025%26creative%3D165953%26creativeASIN%3D0314063781>.
- S. V. Astafiev, A. Z. Snyder, G. L. Shulman, and M. Corbetta. Comment on “modafinil shifts human locus coeruleus to low-tonic, high-phasic activity during functional MRI” and “homeostatic sleep pressure and responses to sustained attention in the suprachiasmatic area”. *Science*, 328(5976):309–309, Apr 2010. doi: 10.1126/science.1177200. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1177200>.
- G. Aston-Jones, J. Rajkowski, P. Kubiak, and T. Alexinsky. Locus coeruleus neurons in monkey are selectively activated by attended cues in a vigilance task. *J Neurosci*, 14(7):4467–4480, Jul 1994.
- Gary Aston-Jones and Jonathan D. Cohen. An integrative theory of locus coeruleus-norepinephrine function: adaptive gain and optimal performance. *Annu Rev Neurosci*, 28:403–450, 2005. doi: 10.1146/annurev.neuro.28.061604.135709. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev.neuro.28.061604.135709>.
- R.H. Baayen, D.J. Davidson, and D.M. Bates. Mixed-effects modeling with crossed random effects for subjects and items. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 59(4):390–412, Nov 2008. doi: 10.1016/j.jml.2007.12.005. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2007.12.005>.
- Debra A. Bangasser, Xiaoyan Zhang, Veraaj Garachh, Emily Hanhauser, and Rita J. Valentino. Sexual dimorphism in locus coeruleus dendritic morphology: a structural basis for sex differences in emotional arousal. *Physiol Behav*, 103(3-4):342–351, Jun 2011. doi: 10.1016/j.physbeh.2011.02.037. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2011.02.037>.
- S. Baron-Cohen, S. Wheelwright, R. Skinner, J. Martin, and E. Clubley. The autism-spectrum quotient (aq): evidence from asperger syndrome/high-functioning autism, males and females, scientists and mathematicians. *J Autism Dev Disord*, 31(1):5–17, Feb 2001.
- Simon Baron-Cohen and Sally Wheelwright. The empathy quotient: an investigation of adults with asperger syndrome or high functioning autism, and normal sex differences. *J Autism Dev Disord*, 34(2):163–175, Apr 2004.
- Simon Baron-Cohen, Jennifer Richler, Dheraj Bisarya, Nishanth Gurunathan, and Sally Wheelwright. The systemizing quotient: an investigation of adults with asperger syndrome or high-functioning autism, and normal sex differences. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*, 358(1430):361–374, Feb 2003. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2002.1206. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2002.1206>.

- David A. Barton, Tye Dawood, Elisabeth A. Lambert, Murray D. Esler, Deepak Haikerwal, Celia Brenchley, Florentia Socratous, David M. Kaye, Markus P. Schlaich, Ian Hickie, and Gavin W. Lambert. Sympathetic activity in major depressive disorder: identifying those at increased cardiac risk? *J Hypertens*, 25(10):2117–2124, Oct 2007. doi: 10.1097/HJH.0b013e32829baae7. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/HJH.0b013e32829baae7>.
- Douglas Bates. [R] - lmer, p-values and all that. stats.ethz.ch, May 2006. URL <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>.
- Douglas M. Bates. Fitting linear mixed models in R. *R News*, (5):27–30, 2005.
- Douglas M. Bates. Linear mixed model implementation in lme4. *Manuscript, University of Wisconsin - Madison*, January 2007.
- Mark G Baxter and Paula L Croxson. Behavioral control by the orbital prefrontal cortex: reversal of fortune. *Nature Neuroscience*, 16(8):984–985, Jul 2013. doi: 10.1038/nn.3472. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nn.3472>.
- Aaron T. Beck, Robert A. Steer, Roberta Ball, and William F. Ranieri. Comparison of beck depression inventories-ia and-ii in psychiatric outpatients. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 67(3):588–597, Dec 1996. doi: 10.1207/s15327752jpa6703_13. URL http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa6703_13.
- E. E. Benarroch. The locus ceruleus norepinephrine system: Functional organization and potential clinical significance. *Neurology*, 73(20):1699–1704, Nov 2009. doi: 10.1212/WNL.0b013e3181c2937c. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0b013e3181c2937c>.
- Pierre Blier and Mostafa El Mansari. The importance of serotonin and noradrenaline in anxiety. *International Journal of Psychiatry in Clinical Practice*, 11(s2):16–23, Jan 2007. doi: 10.1080/13651500701388310. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13651500701388310>.
- Martin Bohus, Nikolaus Kleindienst, Matthias F. Limberger, Rolf-Dieter Stieglitz, Melanie Domsalla, Alexander L. Chapman, Regina Steil, Alexandra Philipsen, and Martina Wolf. The short version of the borderline symptom list (bsl-23): Development and initial data on psychometric properties. *Psychopathology*, 42(1):32–39, 2009. doi: 10.1159/000173701. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1159/000173701>.
- Agnieszka Bojko. Using eye tracking to compare web page designs: A case study. *Journal of Usability Studies*, 1(3):112–120, May 2006.
- Jay C. Bradley, Karl C. Bentley, Aleem I. Mughal, and Sandra M. Brown. Clinical performance of a handheld digital infrared monocular pupillometer for measurement of the dark-adapted pupil diameter. *Journal of Cataract & Refractive Surgery*, 36(2):277–281, Feb 2010. doi: 10.1016/j.jcrs.2009.09.025. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrs.2009.09.025>.
- J. Bradshaw. Pupil size as a measure of arousal during information processing. *Nature*, 216(5114):515–516, Nov 1967.
- M Brant-Zawadzki, G D Gillan, and W R Nitz. Mprage: a three-dimensional, t1-weighted, gradient-echo sequence—initial experience in the brain. *Radiology*, 182(3):769–775, 1992. doi: 10.1148/radiology.182.3.1535892. URL <http://pubs.rsna.org/doi/abs/10.1148/radiology.182.3.1535892>. PMID: 1535892.
- C. E. Bye, M. Clubley, T. Henson, A. W. Peck, S. A. Smith, and S. E. Smith. Changes in the human light reflex as a measure of the anticholinergic effects of drugs. a comparison with other measures. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*, 15(1):21–25, Feb 1979.
- Hale Z. Batur Caglayan, Ilksen A. Colpak, and Tulay Kansu. A diagnostic challenge. *Current Opinion in Ophthalmology*, 24(6):550–557, Nov 2013. doi: 10.1097/ICU.0000000000000005. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/ICU.0000000000000005>.
- Andrea E. Cavanna. The precuneus and consciousness. *CNS Spectr*, 12(7):545–552, Jul 2007.
- J. M. Chambers, A Freeny, and R. M Heiberger. *Statistical Models in S*, volume Chapter 5: Analysis of variance; designed experiments. Wadsworth & Brooks/Cole., 1992.
- R. M. Champan and H. R. Bragdon. Evoked responses to numerical and non-numerical visual stimuli while problem solving. *Nature*, 203:1155–1157, Sep 1964.

- Horea Christian. faceOM - Python and MATLAB scripts for data processing and analysis written for the “neuronal correlates of oculometric parameters in face recognition” research project., 2013a. URL <https://github.com/TheChymera/faceOM>.
- Horea Christian. faceRT - Python script suite. GitHub, 2013b. URL <https://github.com/TheChymera/facesRT>.
- Horea Christian. interstats - Python wrappers for statistical tools with optional L^AT_EX output. GitHub, 2013c. URL <https://github.com/TheChymera/interstats>.
- Horea Christian. pystim - a Python script for automated stimulus sequence calculation. GitHub, 2013d. URL <https://github.com/TheChymera/pystim>.
- Horea Christian. Pyxrand - Python script for shuffling pixels in images. GitHub, 2013e. URL <https://github.com/TheChymera/pyxrand>.
- Horea Christian. questioPy - a Python script for automated questionnaire evaluation. GitHub, 2013f. URL <https://github.com/TheChymera/questioPy>.
- H. Collewijn, C. J. Erkelens, and R. M. Steinman. Binocular co-ordination of human vertical saccadic eye movements. *J Physiol*, 404:183–197, Oct 1988.
- C. A. Conway, B. C. Jones, L. M. DeBruine, A. C. Little, and A. Sahraie. Transient pupil constrictions to faces are sensitive to orientation and species. *Journal of Vision*, 8(3):17–17, Mar 2008. doi: 10.1167/8.3.17. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1167/8.3.17>.
- A Dubois-Poulsen, F Loisillier, and M Loisiller. Un appareil utilisant les convertisseurs d’infra-rouges pour l’etude de la pupille dans l’obscurite absolue. [apparatus using infra-red converters for the study of the pupils in total darkness]. *Bulletin des societes d’ophtalmologie de France*, 3:4–150, March 1955.
- Eran Eldar, Jonathan D Cohen, and Yael Niv. The effects of neural gain on attention and learning. *Nature Neuroscience*, 16(8):1146–1153, Jun 2013. doi: 10.1038/nn.3428. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nn.3428>.
- C. J. Ellis. The pupillary light reflex in normal subjects. *Br J Ophthalmol*, 65(11):754–759, Nov 1981.
- Thomas M Engber, Elizabeth J Koury, Shelley A Dennis, Matthew S Miller, Patricia C Contreras, and Ratan V Bhat. Differential patterns of regional c-fos induction in the rat brain by amphetamine and the novel wakefulness-promoting agent modafinil. *Neuroscience Letters*, 241(2-3):95–98, Jan 1998. doi: 10.1016/S0304-3940(97)00962-2. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3940\(97\)00962-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3940(97)00962-2).
- Kevin T. Fitzgerald and Alvin C. Bronstein. Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor exposure. *Topics in Companion Animal Medicine*, 28(1):13–17, Feb 2013. doi: 10.1053/j.tcam.2013.03.003. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1053/j.tcam.2013.03.003>.
- Michael S. Franklin, James M. Broadway, Michael D. Mrazek, Jonathan Smallwood, and Jonathan W. Schooler. Window to the wandering mind: Pupillometry of spontaneous thought while reading. *The Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, pages 1–15, Oct 2013. doi: 10.1080/17470218.2013.858170. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/17470218.2013.858170>.
- Shai Gabay, Yoni Pertzov, and Avishai Henik. Orienting of attention, pupil size, and the norepinephrine system. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, 73(1):123–129, Jan 2011. doi: 10.3758/s13414-010-0015-4. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3758/s13414-010-0015-4>.
- H. D. Gambill, K. N. Ogle, and T. P. Kearns. Mydriatic effect of four drugs determined with pupillograph. *Arch Ophthalmol*, 77(6):740–746, Jun 1967.
- M. Gesi, P. Soldani, F. S. Giorgi, A. Santinami, I. Bonaccorsi, and F. Fornai. The role of the locus coeruleus in the development of parkinson’s disease. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*, 24(6):655–668, Aug 2000.
- Mark S. Gilzenrat, Sander Nieuwenhuis, Marieke Jepma, and Jonathan D. Cohen. Pupil diameter tracks changes in control state predicted by the adaptive gain theory of locus coeruleus function. *Cognitive, Affective, & Behavioral Neuroscience*, 10(2):252–269, Jun 2010. doi: 10.3758/CABN.10.2.252. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3758/CABN.10.2.252>.

- GitHub Inc. Powerful collaboration, code review, and code management for open source and private projects. online, 2008–present. URL <https://github.com/>.
- B. C. Goldwater. Psychological significance of pupillary movements. *Psychol Bull*, 77(5):340–355, May 1972.
- Eric Granholm and Stuart R. Steinhauser. Pupillometric measures of cognitive and emotional processes. *Int J Psychophysiol*, 52(1):1–6, Mar 2004. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2003.12.001. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2003.12.001>.
- S. J. Grant and DE Redmond, Jr. Neuronal activity of the locus ceruleus in awake macaca arctoides. *Exp Neurol*, 84(3):701–708, Jun 1984.
- Douglas N. Greve. Optseq2 - a tool for automatically scheduling events for event-related fMRI experiments, 2002.
- James J. Gross and Oliver P. John. Individual differences in two emotion regulation processes: implications for affect, relationships, and well-being. *J Pers Soc Psychol*, 85(2):348–362, Aug 2003.
- Ralitza Gueorguieva and John H. Krystal. Move over anova: progress in analyzing repeated-measures data and its reflection in papers published in the archives of general psychiatry. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*, 61(3):310–317, Mar 2004. doi: 10.1001/archpsyc.61.3.310. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.61.3.310>.
- A. R. Hariri, S. Y. Bookheimer, and J. C. Mazziotta. Modulating emotional responses: effects of a neocortical network on the limbic system. *Neuroreport*, 11(1):43–48, Jan 2000.
- Ahmad R. Hariri, Alessandro Tessitore, Venkata S. Mattay, Francesco Fera, and Daniel R. Weinberger. The amygdala response to emotional stimuli: A comparison of faces and scenes. *NeuroImage*, 17(1):317–323, Sep 2002. doi: 10.1006/nimg.2002.1179. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/nimg.2002.1179>.
- Ahmad R. Hariri, Venkata S. Mattay, Alessandro Tessitore, Francesco Fera, and Daniel R. Weinberger. Neocortical modulation of the amygdala response to fearful stimuli. *Biol Psychiatry*, 53(6):494–501, Mar 2003.
- R. J. Harris, A. W. Young, and T. J. Andrews. Morphing between expressions dissociates continuous from categorical representations of facial expression in the human brain. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(51):21164–21169, Dec 2012. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1212207110. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1212207110>.
- V. Hartweg, A. Milbradt, A. Zimmerhofer, and L. F. Hornke. testmaker - a computer software for web-based assessments, 2013. URL http://www.global-assess.rwth-aachen.de/testmaker-wiki/en/index.php/Main_Page.
- T. R. Hayes and A. A. Petrov. Pupillometry as a method for tracking shifts in control state during visual relational reasoning. *Journal of Vision*, 13(9):799–799, Jul 2013. doi: 10.1167/13.9.799. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1167/13.9.799>.
- E. H. Hess and J. M. Polt. Pupil size as related to interest value of visual stimuli. *Science*, 132(3423):349–350, Aug 1960.
- E. H. Hess, A. L. Seltzer, and J. M. Shlien. Pupil response of hetero- and homosexual males to pictures of men and women: A pilot study. *J Abnorm Psychol*, 70:165–168, Jun 1965.
- Jean-Pierre Hornung. The human raphe nuclei and the serotonergic system. *Journal of Chemical Neuroanatomy*, 26(4):331–343, Dec 2003. doi: 10.1016/j.jchemneu.2003.10.002. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jchemneu.2003.10.002>.
- R. H. Hou, C. Freeman, R. W. Langley, E. Szabadi, and C. M. Bradshaw. Does modafinil activate the locus coeruleus in man? comparison of modafinil and clonidine on arousal and autonomic functions in human volunteers. *Psychopharmacology (Berl)*, 181(3):537–549, Sep 2005. doi: 10.1007/s00213-005-0013-8. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00213-005-0013-8>.
- Cédric M. Hysek and Matthias E. Liechti. Effects of mdma alone and after pretreatment with reboxetine, duloxetine, clonidine, carvedilol, and doxazosin on pupillary light reflex. *Psychopharmacology (Berl)*, 224(3):363–376, Dec 2012. doi: 10.1007/s00213-012-2761-6. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00213-012-2761-6>.
- Eric Jones, Travis Oliphant, Pearu Peterson, et al. SciPy: Open source scientific tools for Python, 2001–present. URL <http://www.scipy.org/>.

- Noam I. Keren, Carl T. Lozar, Kelly C. Harris, Paul S. Morgan, and Mark A. Eckert. In vivo mapping of the human locus coeruleus. *NeuroImage*, 47(4):1261–1267, Oct 2009. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2009.06.012. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2009.06.012>.
- J. G. Kerns. Anterior cingulate conflict monitoring and adjustments in control. *Science*, 303(5660):1023–1026, Feb 2004. doi: 10.1126/science.1089910. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1089910>.
- Ronald C Kessler, Lenard Adler, Minnie Ames, Olga Demler, Steve Faraone, Eva Hiripi, Mary J Howes, Robert Jin, Kristina Secnik, Thomas Spencer, et al. The world health organization adult adhd self-report scale (asrs): a short screening scale for use in the general population. *Psychological medicine*, 35(02):245–256, 2005. URL http://journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0033291704002892.
- Hannah E. Kirk, Darren R. Hocking, Deborah M. Riby, and Kim M. Cornish. Linking social behaviour and anxiety to attention to emotional faces in williams syndrome. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 34(12):4608–4616, Dec 2013. doi: 10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.042. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.042>.
- C Klein, B Andresen, and T Jahn. Erfassung der schizotypen persönlichkeit nach dsm-iii-r: Psychometrische eigenschaften einer autorisierten deutschsprachigen Übersetzung des “schizotypal personality questionnaire” (spq) von raine. *Diagnostica*, (43): 347–369, 1997.
- Wendy Klein-Schwartz, Blaine E. Benson, Samantha C. Lee, and Toby Litovitz. Comparison of citalopram and other selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor ingestions in children. *Clinical Toxicology*, 50(5):418–423, Jun 2012. doi: 10.3109/15563650.2012.678497. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/15563650.2012.678497>.
- W. P. Koella and U. Schaeppi. The reaction of the isolated cat iris to serotonin. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*, 138:154–158, Nov 1962.
- Susanne Kraemer, Heidi Danker-Hopfe, Hans Dorn, Andrea Schmidt, Ingrid Ehlert, and Werner M Herrmann. Time-of-day variations of indicators of attention: performance, physiologic parameters, and self-assessment of sleepiness. *Biological Psychiatry*, 48(11):1069–1080, Dec 2000. doi: 10.1016/S0006-3223(00)00908-2. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223\(00\)00908-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3223(00)00908-2).
- Bruno Laeng, Marte Ørbo, Terje Holmlund, and Michele Miozzo. Pupillary stroop effects. *Cognitive Processing*, 12(1):13–21, Feb 2011. doi: 10.1007/s10339-010-0370-z. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10339-010-0370-z>.
- Michael Lewis and Andrew Edmonds. Searching for faces in scrambled scenes. *Visual Cognition*, 12(7):1309–1336, Oct 2005. doi: 10.1080/13506280444000535. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13506280444000535>.
- Irene Loewenfeld and Otto Lowenstein. Mechanisms of reflex dilation of the pupil - historical review and experimental analysis. *Documenta Ophthalmologica*, 1958.
- Sandra E. Loughlin, Stephen L. Foote, and James H. Fallon. Locus coeruleus projections to cortex: Topography, morphology and collateralization. *Brain Research Bulletin*, 9(1-6):287–294, Jul 1982. doi: 10.1016/0361-9230(82)90142-3. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0361-9230\(82\)90142-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0361-9230(82)90142-3).
- Richard J. Maddock, Amy S. Garrett, and Michael H. Buonocore. Posterior cingulate cortex activation by emotional words: fmri evidence from a valence decision task. *Human Brain Mapping*, 18(1):30–41, Jan 2003. doi: 10.1002/hbm.10075. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/hbm.10075>.
- T. Maeda. The locus coeruleus: history. *J Chem Neuroanat*, 18(1-2):57–64, Feb 2000.
- J.K. Mai and G. Paxinos. *The Human Nervous System*. Academic Press, 2011. URL <http://www.amazon.com/The-Human-Nervous-System-Juergen-ebook/dp/B007QRPTRE%3FSubscriptionId%3D0JYN1NVW651KCA56C102%26tag%3Dtchkie-20%26linkCode%3Dxm2%26camp%3D2025%26creative%3D165953%26creativeASIN%3DB007QRPTRE>.
- Joseph A. Maldjian, Paul J. Laurienti, Robert A. Kraft, and Jonathan H. Burdette. An automated method for neuroanatomic and cytoarchitectonic atlas-based interrogation of fmri data sets. *NeuroImage*, 19(3):1233–1239, Jul 2003. doi: 10.1016/S1053-8119(03)00169-1. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1053-8119\(03\)00169-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1053-8119(03)00169-1).

- Mark F. Mehler and Dominick P. Purpura. Autism, fever, epigenetics and the locus coeruleus. *Brain Research Reviews*, 59(2): 388–392, Mar 2009. doi: 10.1016/j.brainresrev.2008.11.001. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresrev.2008.11.001>.
- Michael J. Minzenberg, Andrew J. Watrous, Jong H. Yoon, Stefan Ursu, and Cameron S. Carter. Modafinil shifts human locus coeruleus to low-tonic, high-phasic activity during functional mri. *Science*, 322(5908):1700–1702, Dec 2008. doi: 10.1126/science.1164908. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1164908>.
- Y. Morad, H. Lemberg, N. Yofe, and Y. Dagan. Pupilligraphy as an objective indicator of fatigue. *Curr Eye Res*, 21(1):535–542, Jul 2000.
- Peter R. Mouton, Bente Pakkenberg, Hans JÃ,rgen G. Gundersen, and Donald L. Price. Absolute number and size of pigmented locus coeruleus neurons in young and aged individuals. *Journal of Chemical Neuroanatomy*, 7(3):185 – 190, 1994. ISSN 0891-0618. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0891-0618\(94\)90028-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0891-0618(94)90028-0). URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0891061894900280>.
- Peter R. Murphy, Ian H. Robertson, Joshua H. Balsters, and Redmond G. O’connell. Pupillometry and p3 index the locus coeruleus-noradrenergic arousal function in humans. *Psychophysiology*, 48(11):1532–1543, Nov 2011. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8986.2011.01226.x. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8986.2011.01226.x>.
- R. B. Murray and M. H. Loughnane. Infrared video pupillometry: a method used to measure the pupillary effects of drugs in small laboratory animals in real time. *J Neurosci Methods*, 3(4):365–375, Apr 1981.
- P. Nagele. Misuse of standard error of the mean (sem) when reporting variability of a sample. a critical evaluation of four anaesthesia journals. *Br J Anaesth*, 90(4):514–516, Apr 2003.
- Anette Green Nielsen, Rasmus Steen Pedersen, Lene Noehr-Jensen, Per Damkier, and Kim Broesen. Two separate dose-dependent effects of paroxetine: mydriasis and inhibition of tramadol’s o-demethylation via cyp2d6. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 66(7):655–660, Jul 2010. doi: 10.1007/s00228-010-0803-8. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00228-010-0803-8>.
- L. Noehr-Jensen, S. T. Zwisler, F. Larsen, S. H. Sindrup, P. Damkier, F. Nielsen, and K. Broesen. Impact of cyp2C19 phenotypes on escitalopram metabolism and an evaluation of pupillometry as a serotonergic biomarker. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 65(9):887–894, Sep 2009. doi: 10.1007/s00228-009-0657-0. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00228-009-0657-0>.
- J C Nunally, P D Knott, A Duchnowski, and R Parker. Pupillary response as a general measure of activation. *Perception and Psychophysics*, 2:149–155, 1967.
- Travis E. Oliphant. Python for scientific computing. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 9(3):10–20, May 2007. doi: 10.1109/MCSE.2007.58. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2007.58>.
- Jonathan W. Peirce. Generating stimuli for neuroscience using psychopy. *Front Neuroinform*, 2:10, 2008. doi: 10.3389/neuro.11.010.2008. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/neuro.11.010.2008>.
- Robert A. Philibert, Olga Zadorozhnyaya, Steven R.H. Beach, and Gene H. Brody. Comparison of the genotyping results using DNA obtained from blood and saliva. *Psychiatric Genetics*, 18(6):275–281, Dec 2008. doi: 10.1097/YPG.0b013e3283060f81. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/YPG.0b013e3283060f81>.
- M. A. Phillips, E. Szabadi, and C. M. Bradshaw. Comparison of the effects of clonidine and yohimbine on spontaneous pupillary fluctuations in healthy human volunteers. *Psychopharmacology (Berl)*, 150(1):85–89, May 2000.
- T. W. Picton. The p300 wave of the human event-related potential. *J Clin Neurophysiol*, 9(4):456–479, Oct 1992.
- Jose Pinheiro, Douglas Bates, Saikat DebRoy, Deepayan Sarkar, and R Core Team. *nlme: Linear and Nonlinear Mixed Effects Models*, 2013. R package version 3.1-111.
- Tepring Piquado, Derek Isaacowitz, and Arthur Wingfield. Pupillometry as a measure of cognitive effort in younger and older adults. *Psychophysiology*, 47(3):560–569, May 2010. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8986.2009.00947.x. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8986.2009.00947.x>.

- Kerstin Preuschoff, Bernard Marius 't Hart, and Wolfgang Einhäuser. Pupil dilation signals surprise: Evidence for noradrenaline's role in decision making. *Front Neurosci*, 5:115, 2011. doi: 10.3389/fnins.2011.00115. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2011.00115>.
- PyData Development. Pandas - an open source, BSD-licensed library providing high-performance, easy-to-use data structures and data analysis tools for Python., 2008–present. URL <http://pandas.pydata.org/>.
- R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2013. URL <http://www.R-project.org>.
- Marcus E. Raichle and Abraham Z. Snyder. A default mode of brain function: A brief history of an evolving idea. *NeuroImage*, 37(4):1083–1090, Oct 2007. doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2007.02.041. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2007.02.041>.
- A. Raine. The spq: A scale for the assessment of schizotypal personality based on DSM-iii-r criteria. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 17(4):555–564, Jan 1991. doi: 10.1093/schbul/17.4.555. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/schbul/17.4.555>.
- J. Rajkowski. Activation of monkey locus coeruleus neurons varies with difficulty and performance in a target detection task. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 92(1):361–371, Mar 2004. doi: 10.1152/jn.00673.2003. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1152/jn.00673.2003>.
- J. Rajkowski, P. Kubiak, and G. Aston-Jones. Locus coeruleus activity in monkey: phasic and tonic changes are associated with altered vigilance. *Brain Res Bull*, 35(5-6):607–616, 1994.
- Sam S. Rakover and Baruch Cahlon. Cognitive processing of scrambled faces. *Am J Psychol*, 126(2):235–244, 2013.
- T. C. Ruch and J. F. Fulton. *Medical physiology and biophysics*. W. B. Saunders Company, Philadelphia, Pa, 1960.
- E. R. Samuels and E. Szabadi. Functional neuroanatomy of the noradrenergic locus coeruleus: its roles in the regulation of arousal and autonomic function part ii: physiological and pharmacological manipulations and pathological alterations of locus coeruleus activity in humans. *Curr Neuropharmacol*, 6(3):254–285, Sep 2008. doi: 10.2174/157015908785777193. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/157015908785777193>.
- Jonathan Smallwood, Kevin S. Brown, Christine Tipper, Barry Giesbrecht, Michael S. Franklin, Michael D. Mrazek, Jean M. Carlson, and Jonathan W. Schooler. Pupillometric evidence for the decoupling of attention from perceptual input during offline thought. *PLoS ONE*, 6(3):e18298, Mar 2011. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0018298. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0018298>.
- Jolinda Smith. on-line, 2010. URL <http://lcni.uoregon.edu/~jolinda/MRICConvert/>.
- S. A. Smith and S. E. Smith. Factors determining the potency of cholinomimetic miotic drugs and their effect upon the light reflex in man. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*, 6(2):149–153, Aug 1978.
- Stephen M. Stigler. Francis galton's account of the invention of correlation. *Statistical Science*, 4(2):73–79, May 1989. doi: 10.1214/ss/1177012580. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1214/ss/1177012580>.
- D. L. Streiner. Maintaining standards: differences between the standard deviation and standard error, and when to use each. *Can J Psychiatry*, 41(8):498–502, Oct 1996.
- S. A. Taylor. Proceedings: Quantitative studies on acetylcholine receptors of the isolated iris sphincter muscle. *J Physiol*, 239(1):6P–7P, May 1974.
- A. Terry Bahill and Lawrence Stark. Neurological control of horizontal and vertical components of oblique saccadic eye movements. *Mathematical Biosciences*, 27(3-4):287–298, Jan 1975. doi: 10.1016/0025-5564(75)90107-8. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564\(75\)90107-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564(75)90107-8).
- N. Theofilopoulos, J. Longmore, F. A. Kerr, E. Szabadi, and C. M. Bradshaw. Consensual pupillary responses to mydriatic and miotic drugs. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*, 26(6):697–702, Dec 1988.

- S. Thompson. Pupillometry: A clinical measure of retinal function in inherited disease. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science*, 53(9):5570–5570, Aug 2012. doi: 10.1167/iovs.12-10616. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1167/iovs.12-10616>.
- Nim Tottenham, James W. Tanaka, Andrew C. Leon, Thomas McCarry, Marcella Nurse, Todd A. Hare, David J. Marcus, Alissa Westerlund, B. J. Casey, and Charles Nelson. The nimstim set of facial expressions: judgments from untrained research participants. *Psychiatry Res*, 168(3):242–249, Aug 2009. doi: 10.1016/j.psychres.2008.05.006. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2008.05.006>.
- G. W. van Alphen. The adrenergic receptors of the intraocular muscles of the human eye. *Invest Ophthalmol*, 15(6):502–505, Jun 1976.
- P. H. van Domburg and H. J. ten Donkelaar. The human substantia nigra and ventral tegmental area. a neuroanatomical study with notes on aging and aging diseases. *Adv Anat Embryol Cell Biol*, 121:1–132, 1991.
- B. Walter, C. Blecker, P. Kirsch, G. Sammer, A. Schienle, R. Stark, and D. Vaitl. Marina: An easy to use tool for the creation of masks for region of interest analyses. *9th International Conference on Functional Mapping of the Human Brain*, June 2003.
- J. M. Weiss, J. C. Stout, M. F. Aaron, N. Quan, M. J. Owens, P. D. Butler, and C. B. Nemeroff. Depression and anxiety: role of the locus coeruleus and corticotropin-releasing factor. *Brain Res Bull*, 35(5-6):561–572, 1994.
- Wellcome Trust Centre for Neuroimaging. SPM - a software package for the analysis of brain imaging data sequences. URL <http://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm/>.
- P. J. Whalen. Human amygdala responsivity to masked fearful eye whites. *Science*, 306(5704):2061–2061, Dec 2004. doi: 10.1126/science.1103617. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.1103617>.
- E. Woldemussie, B. J. Feldmann, and J. Chen. Characterization of muscarinic receptors in cultured human iris sphincter and ciliary smooth muscle cells. *Exp Eye Res*, 56(4):385–392, Apr 1993. doi: 10.1006/exer.1993.1052. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/exer.1993.1052>.
- Agnieszka Wykowska, Christine Anderl, Anna Schubö, and Bernhard Hommel. Motivation modulates visual attention: Evidence from pupillometry. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 2013. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00059. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00059>.
- T. Yoshitomi, Y. Ito, and H. Inomata. Adrenergic excitatory and cholinergic inhibitory innervations in the human iris dilator. *Exp Eye Res*, 40(3):453–459, Mar 1985.
- R. E. Yoss, N. J. Moyer, and R. W. Hollenhorst. Pupil size and spontaneous pupillary waves associated with alertness, drowsiness, and sleep. *Neurology*, 20(6):545–554, Jun 1970.
- Yongxin Yu, Andrew G Ramage, and Michael C Koss. Pharmacological studies of 8-oh-dpat-induced pupillary dilation in anesthetized rats. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, 489(3):207–213, Apr 2004. doi: 10.1016/j.ejphar.2004.03.007. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2004.03.007>.
- Adriana A. Zekveld, Sophia E. Kramer, and Joost M. Festen. Cognitive load during speech perception in noise: The influence of age, hearing loss, and cognition on the pupil response. *Ear and Hearing*, 32(4):498–510, Jul 2011. doi: 10.1097/AUD.0b013e31820512bb. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/AUD.0b013e31820512bb>.
- Sheng Zhang and Matthew Turk. Eigenfaces. *Scholarpedia*, 3(9):4244, 2008. doi: 10.4249/scholarpedia.4244. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.4249/scholarpedia.4244>.

Chapter 7

Supplementary Material

$$\sigma_{x,y} = \sqrt{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2} = \sqrt{2\sigma_x^2} \approx \sqrt{2 \cdot (0.68K)^2} \approx 0.96K$$

Figure 7.1: Here we calculate the standard deviation (σ) of the distance from the original pixel location to the new pixel location following kernel-based scrambling, as detailed in section 3.3.2.2. The standard deviation along one axis is defined as $0.68K$ (68% of the scrambling kernel, K) following the 68–95–99.7 rule, though experimentally we have found slightly lower values ($\approx 0.6K$).

$$\Pr(\mu - \sigma \leq x \leq \mu + \sigma) \approx 0.6827$$

$$\Pr(\mu - 2\sigma \leq x \leq \mu + 2\sigma) \approx 0.9545$$

$$\Pr(\mu - 3\sigma \leq x \leq \mu + 3\sigma) \approx 0.9973$$

Figure 7.2: The general expression of the three-sigma rule, in mathematical notation, for x being an observation from a normally distributed random variable, μ being the mean of the distribution, and σ being its standard deviation. The three-sigma rule (also known as the “68–95–99.7 rule”) states that nearly all values lie within 3 standard deviations of the mean in a normal distribution.

	Model 1
(Intercept)	1.16 (0.06)***
CoI:happy	-0.03 (0.04)
dTime:S02	0.08 (0.04)*
dTime:S03	0.08 (0.04)*
dTime:S04	0.09 (0.04)*
dTime:S05	0.04 (0.04)
dTime:S06	0.01 (0.04)
dTime:S07	0.00 (0.04)
dTime:S08	-0.05 (0.04)
CoI:happy:dTime:S02	-0.03 (0.06)
CoI:happy:dTime:S03	-0.03 (0.06)
CoI:happy:dTime:S04	-0.04 (0.06)
CoI:happy:dTime:S05	-0.01 (0.06)
CoI:happy:dTime:S06	-0.02 (0.06)
CoI:happy:dTime:S07	-0.03 (0.06)
CoI:happy:dTime:S08	0.03 (0.06)
Num. obs.	192

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Table 7.1: Mixed model fitted to the latter half of the time course depicted in figure 5.6. The independent variable is CoI (condition of interest) which is either "hard" or "difficult". Time and ID (participant) are defined as random variables.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A(h) &= \frac{R^2}{2} \left[2 \arccos \left(1 - \frac{h}{R} \right) - \sin \left(2 \arccos \left(1 - \frac{h}{R} \right) \right) \right] \\
 &= R^2 \left[\arccos \left(1 - \frac{h}{R} \right) - \left(1 - \frac{h}{R} \right) \sqrt{2 \frac{h}{R} - \frac{h^2}{R^2}} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 7.3: The area of a circle segment A defined relative to the height of that segment, h - with R as the circle radius. We use this as a function for how much of the pupil area will be lost relative to how far an eyelid covers it. For the sake of simplicity we approximate the eyelid with a straight rather than very slightly curved line.

7.1 Non-Definitive Preliminary Experiment Runs

Figure 7.4: Reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed with composite cluster and kernel based scrambling, with a constant kernel of 6 px and clusters of the sizes indicated in the graphic (sizes given in pixels). Reaction times for non-response trials were counted as 5 s. The error bars represent the standard deviation.

Conditions of interest	Proposed best estimators (scrambling cluster sizes in px)				
	11	15	19	23	27
emotion-easy	2.8×10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-1}	3.8×10^{-1}	8.5×10^{-1}	6.4×10^{-1}
emotion-hard	2.3×10^{-1}	1.5×10^{-1}	2.5×10^{-2}	4.1×10^{-2}	2.9×10^{-2}

Table 7.2: Table of two-tailed paired sample t-test p -values for the data in figure 7.4, testing the probability of our observations if the compared conditions share the same mean. Note that - though unorthodox - this test does not lose accuracy due to multiple comparisons. As we are looking for the group least likely to reject the null hypothesis, multiple comparison actually makes the test more stringent.

Figure 7.5: Reaction times for Hariri-style face matching. Scrambled images for simple visual recognition were preprocessed with composite cluster and kernel based scrambling, with a constant kernel of 6 px and clusters of the sizes indicated in the graphic (sizes given in pixels). Reaction times for non-response trials were counted as 5s. The error bars represent the standard deviation.

Conditions of interest	Proposed best estimators (scrambling cluster sizes in px)				
	6	10	14	18	22
emotion-easy	3.1×10^{-4}	4.8×10^{-3}	1.2×10^{-1}	1.3×10^{-1}	8.0×10^{-2}
emotion-hard	1.5×10^{-2}	6.4×10^{-1}	9.7×10^{-2}	1.1×10^{-1}	1.0×10^{-1}

Table 7.3: Table of two-tailed paired sample t-test p -values for the data in figure 7.5, testing the probability of our observations if the compared conditions share the same mean. Note that - though unorthodox - this test does not lose accuracy due to multiple comparisons. As we are looking for the group least likely to reject the null hypothesis, multiple comparison actually makes the test more stringent.

	Model 1
(Intercept)	2.10 [1.86; 2.34]*
CoI:scrambling-10	-0.22 [-0.33; -0.11]*
CoI:scrambling-14	-0.45 [-0.57; -0.34]*
CoI:scrambling-18	-0.45 [-0.56; -0.34]*
CoI:scrambling-22	-0.45 [-0.56; -0.34]*
Num. obs.	1120
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.07
Variance: Residual	0.36

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 7.4: Mixed model fitted to the raw data depicted in figure 7.4. Our factors are the conditions of interest (CoI), excluding the emotion recognition trials. The model chooses the first factor (scrambling-06) as the base intercept. Note the downwards trend for the first 3 factors and that the last 3 factors' values land confidence intervals are almost identical.

	Model 1
(Intercept)	0.04 [0.00; 0.07]*
difficulty:hard	0.04 [0.00; 0.07]*
scrambled:yes	-0.03 [-0.07; 0.00]
Num. obs.	28
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.00
Variance: Residual	0.00

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 7.5: Linear model fitted to the raw error rate data depicted in figure 4.6. Our factors are scrambling (yes or no) and difficulty (easy or hard) - not including their interaction. The model chooses "easy" and "not scrambled" as the intercept value.

	Model 1
(Intercept)	0.02 [-0.01; 0.05]
difficulty:hard	0.04 [0.00; 0.07]
Num. obs.	28
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.00
Variance: Residual	0.00

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 7.6: Linear model fitted to the raw error rate data depicted in figure 4.6. Our factor is and difficulty (easy or hard). The model chooses "easy" as the intercept value

Model 1	
(Intercept)	0.05 [0.02; 0.08]*
scrambled:yes	-0.03 [-0.07; 0.01]
Num. obs.	28
Num. groups: ID	7
Variance: ID.(Intercept)	0.00
Variance: Residual	0.00

* 0 outside the confidence interval

Table 7.7: Linear model fitted to the raw error rate data depicted in figure 4.6. Our factors are scrambling (yes or no). The model chooses "not scrambled" as the intercept value.

This document is versioned via Git and the latest version is available in `.tex` format at
<https://github.com/TheChymera/masterarbeit>

This document is formatted for open publication review loosely based on the guidelines of **OPR** detailed at
<https://github.com/TheChymera/OPR.Concepts-Guidelines-for-OPR>.

All original content present in this work is available under a “Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported License”.